

“Experiment to determine the effects of ‘Status Inflation’ on individual decision making; can an economic boom have adverse outcomes on society?”

Submitted by *Nicholas Stuart Augustus HOWAT*

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“I certify that all material in this dissertation which is not my own work has been identified and that no material is included for which a degree has previously been conferred upon me.”

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Signature:.....

Nicholas S A Howat BA(Hons) GDipAg MBA MRAU FIH
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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to establish that in theory, there is at work in society a mechanism that causes individuals to take additional risk in their decision making in order to maintain or increase their relative status. Furthermore, this hypothesis suggests that the fear of falling behind contemporaries or other individuals endowed with similar levels of status is equivalent to fear of a "loss" and therefore provides significant motivation to act in a manner that avoids any such loss of status. The progression of the idea is that the desire to "not lose" combines with the "high-stakes", "winner-takes-all", output maximising strategies of the modern office environment, with the theoretical result of unanticipated irrational behaviours. These behaviours, far from fulfilling the utility maximisation objectives of the incentive schemes, create internalities and negative externalities that ultimately can cause the self-destruction seen in market crashes. The theory is known as *Status Inflation*. It is postulated that the effects of *Status Inflation* are especially pronounced in firms where the competitive advantage of one individual over another has been almost eliminated by the convergence of education, skills and information (through selection of only the brightest and the best candidates), and where time remains stubbornly finite.

The paper investigates whether any evidence for the theory exists both in terms of existing literature, but also through empirical testing. Status being extremely subjective makes field tests for its presence difficult, costly and/or likely to be highly qualitative, requiring numerous interviews with subjects and subsequent normalisation of results. For this reason an experiment has been devised to test for status inflation called "*The Loan Game*".

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INTRODUCTION

1. BACKGROUND AND INTRODUCTION

DISSERTATION TITLE

"Experiment to determine the effects of 'Status Inflation' on individual decision making; can an economic boom have adverse outcomes on society?"

Economists globally are familiar, to a greater or lesser extent, with the award winning work of Kahneman and Tversky (1979 and 1986) and their observations as to how participants in markets can act in an apparently irrational manner, whilst pursuing what is traditionally regarded as the rational activity of utility maximisation. They were, as this paper is, especially interested in decision making *"under risk"* and when these decisions are based on a probability of outcomes that is obscured or difficult to calculate.

This thesis is concerned with the apparent conflict of certain utility maximising actions of the individual that irrationally jeopardise the wellbeing of their firm/employer or society at large, effectively the scenario of *"biting-the-hand-that-feeds"* or *"killing-the-goose-that laid-the-golden-egg"*. The fact that several such idioms already exist in the English language suggests that this is not just a contemporary problem. Furthermore, the inference from these idioms is that they are observations of, or prophetic warnings against, short-sighted or narrow-minded behaviour that is in itself dubious, foolish, self-centred, questionable or likely to invoke a *"right-minded person's"* disapproval. At its heart, this dissertation is an examination of the motivations of such actions, that its hypotheses are the result of something known as *"Status Inflation"* (a brand new term), which it aims to confirm the existence of, and identify through experiment, its relative strength in an economics context.

The primary question therefore is *"What is Status Inflation?"* In the first instance it is useful to try and derive a definition.

STATUS INFLATION

If we break down the two words and examine them individually through a straight forward exploration of English language, we discover firstly that *Status* is:

"noun

1. *relative social or professional position; standing:*

an improvement in the status of women

- *[mass noun] high rank or social standing: those who enjoy wealth and status*
- *the official classification given to a person, country, or organization, determining their rights or responsibilities: the duchy had been elevated to the status of a principality*

2. *the situation at a particular time during a process:*

an update on the status of the bill

- *a posting on a social networking website that indicates a user's current situation, state of mind, or opinion about something:
when I updated my status on Facebook yesterday I said I was 'seeking a sense of purpose'*

[as modifier]:

I noticed that there were some interesting status updates from some of my local friends

Origin:

late 18th century (as a legal term meaning 'legal standing'): from Latin, literally 'standing', from stare 'to stand'". (Oxford Dictionaries 2013)

The use of the word *relative* in the first description is key so far as *Status Inflation* is concerned. However, the second definition is also interesting on two levels: firstly, the idea that it is *the "situation at a particular time during a process"* suggests movement that, in this case, *Status* is current in one position, but that it is subject to change; and secondly, the seamless transition of *Status* into modern communications terminology, referring to *"Status Updates"*, highlighting the significance and immediacy of *Status* in the modern context.

In the breakdown of the phrase to the second word, we are told that *inflation* is defined as:

"noun

[mass noun]

1. *the action of inflating something or the condition of being inflated:*
the inflation of a balloon
the gross inflation of salaries
 - *Astronomy (in some theories of cosmology) a very brief exponential expansion of the universe postulated to have interrupted the standard linear expansion shortly after the Big Bang.*
2. *Economics a general increase in prices and fall in the purchasing value of money:*
policies aimed at controlling inflation
tax allowances and excise duties were increased in line with inflation
a reduction in annual inflation from 84 per cent to 7 per cent
[as modifier]:
high inflation rates.

Origin:

Middle English (in the sense 'the condition of being inflated with a gas'): from Latin inflatio(n-), from inflare 'blow in to' (see inflate). sense 2 dates from the mid-19th century" (Oxford Dictionaries 2013)

As far as *inflation* is concerned, clearly the second definition is more pertinent to this discussion (although the reference to "...a very brief exponential expansion..." is also an interesting observation), with the notion of a "*general increase in prices and a fall in the purchasing value of money*". Here, both components of the definition are highly relevant, on either side of the same coin. Not only is there an increase in something (in the case of the definition – prices), but there is also a corresponding fall in something else (the purchasing value of money).

Status Inflation follows a similar pattern and can be defined by reversal of the order of the two definitions to be:

"The act of inflating the relative social or professional position (standing) of others around you or the condition of the relative standing of others around you being inflated, causing a reduction or lessening of one's own status relative to the crowd"

to which may be added, *"at, and limited to a certain duration or point in time"*.

Status is therefore neither finite nor is it perpetual, it may be endowed and then increased or decreased, gained or lost. Status inflation is like an economic, financial and social tide that rises around an object; if the object is buoyant it will float and rise with the tide, if it is not (or it is anchored to the bottom through a lack of social mobility) it will be over taken and swamped by that tide.

ECONOMIC BOOMS AND ADVERSE OUTCOMES

In order to answer the question posed, having established what is meant by *Status Inflation*, it is now necessary to explore what is meant by *"adverse outcomes"* with reference to *"can an economic boom have adverse outcomes on society?"* In order to do this and more fully explain the notion of *Status Inflation*, it is necessary to explore where the initial idea was formed and how the concept was developed from there.

In 2003 Mervin King, the then Governor of The Bank of England described the prolonged period of growth since the early/mid-nineteen nineties as the

"non-inflationary consistently expansionary - or "nice" - decade; a decade in which growth was a little above trend, unemployment fell steadily, and, supported by the improved terms of trade, real take-home pay rose without adding to employers' costs, thus allowing consumption to grow at above trend rates without putting upward pressure on inflation." (M. King 2003).

This period and on through to 2007 is also sometimes referred to as "The Great Moderation", highlighted by Ben Bernanke in a 2004 speech to the Eastern Economic Association, but was originally based on work by Chang-Jin and Nelson that studied the US economy in the 1980s (Chang-Jin and Nelson 1999).

On the face of it, this appeared to be a strong economic period with output and wealth increasing across the economy as a whole. This stable period that appeared to have the potential to continue indefinitely

"April 21 2004, [Gordon Brown] remarks at the British Chambers of Commerce annual conference "And it is important we understand how and why it is Britain – once the most stop go of economies - which has avoided the recessions that hit America, Germany, Japan, Italy and most other industrial economies during the world downturn of the last few years and has enjoyed sustained and sustainable growth."" (Guardian 2008)

However, the end of this boom was punctuated by what has now passed into common parlance as *"The Credit Crisis"* or *"Crunch"*, in mid-2007, and was the beginning of what has been termed as the *"Global Recession of 2009"* (Gore 2010), also known as *"the Great Recession"* according to Catherine Rampell (2009), of the New York Times. The Federal Reserve Bank of Minneapolis (2013) described this period as *"the deepest recession in the post war period; at their lowest points employment fell by 6.3 per cent and output fell by 5.1 percent"*, while Ambrose Evans-Pritchard, writing in the Telegraph in March 2009 wrote

"...we have seen industrial production collapse in every region. The drops in January were: Japan (-31pc), Korea (-26pc), Russia (-16pc), Brazil (-15pc), Italy (-14pc), Germany (-12pc). Falls that took two years from late 1929 have been compressed into five months. Those who say this is nothing like the Great Depression are complacent. Household debt is higher today, and UK banks are in worse shape. (No bank of size failed in the British Empire during the slump). Britain's economy contracted by 5.6pc from peak to trough in the early 1930s (Eichengreen). Some put the figure at nearer 8pc..." (Telegraph 2009)

So what went so badly wrong? Evans-Pritchard goes on to identify the causes

"...The errors that led to our current predicament are well-known. A small army of economists – Austrians, Monetarists, and Keynesians – warned that central banks were playing with fire by fixing the price of credit too low and ignoring asset bubbles. The \$6.7 trillion in reserve accumulation by China, Japan, and the petro-powers drove bond yields too low for safety. Credit signals were gravely distorted. In Britain, Gordon Brown poured petrol on the fire by pushing the fiscal deficit to 3pc of GDP at the top of the cycle." (Telegraph 2009)

ASSET BUBBLES

Looking at one specific element "Asset Bubbles" (that this paper will follow through to experimentation), it seems reasonable to accept the 2013 Congressional Budget Office's definition as:

"An economic development in which the price of a class of physical or financial assets...rises to a level that appears to be unsustainable and well above the assets' value as determined by economic fundamentals". (Congressional Budget Office 2013)

Whether one's view of an asset bubble's creation follows the Keynesian *animal spirits*, *unavoidable* event school of thought or the Austrian school's notion that government (or central bank) meddling is typically causal, what seems common to all asset bubbles is that individual investors or actors, through provision of funds for investment into the specific asset class, do so knowing that the bubble will one day burst (unless they are a delusional politician). Yet they still provide investment funds (usually at an accelerating rate), which in turn promotes the self-fulfilling prophecy of the bubble. That is until confidence, for whatever reason, disappears and the inevitable crash occurs. This study considers there are actions afoot that are contrary to Napoleon's assertion that one should, *"never ascribe to conspiracy that which is adequately explained by incompetence"* (Napoleon Bonaparte circa 1800).

INTERNALITIES AND MELIORATION

The foregoing self-destructive scenario has been recognised previously, as indicated by the idioms mentioned and is technically described (in part) in economic terms as an issue with "Internalities" described by Herrnstein et al (1993):

*"Volunteer subjects worked for money in six procedures in which the probability of a payment from either of two alternatives was 1.0, but the rate of pay (i.e. the speed with which a payment was delivered or the size of the payment) interacted with the subjects' recent allocation of choices, which we define as the 'internalities'. **Because of the internalities, choosing the currently more profitable alternative did not maximize total earnings. Subjects were more likely to fail to maximize when the interaction between present pay and past choices was spread over longer sequences of choices, or when the reward variable was the speed, rather than the value, of each payment. Subjects often disregarded the internalities and were instead guided by the current yields of the two alternatives, which is a frequently observed tendency, called 'melioration', in experiments on choices by animals. The tendency toward melioration was only partially counteracted by explicit instructions on how to maximize earnings.**"* (Herrnstein et al 1993)

The problem with outcomes driven by internalities and melioration is that there are victims, both on the inside of the action (those directly "killing-the-goose-that-laid-the-golden-egg") and often on the outside who had no direct involvement in the action, possibly shareholders, pension holders, other employees, depositors, creditors, the public and so on.

Bribes Against The Innocent

Psalm 15 asks the rhetorical question of "Lord, who may dwell in your sacred tent?" and then answers with a list that naturally enough includes the blameless, the righteous, the truthful, but interestingly (particularly in the contemporary context), "...who lends money to the poor without interest; **who does not accept a bribe against the innocent...**" (Holy Bible NIV translation Psalm 15:1-5, 2011). This paper contends that a "bribe against the innocent" might very well be abuse of position, and be compared to receiving a bonus or taking a personal payment that rewards the individual in the short term, but say, damages those others outside the transaction, such as the firm's other employees and shareholders, in the long run?

MOTIVATIONS

One can only assume that the motivation of employees to continue on such a path of collective financially suicidal behaviour is the prospect of earning more money (either through bonuses or promotion). As Balzac pithily wrote *"at the origin of every fortune lies a crime"* (La Comédie Humaine, Honore de Balzac circa 1830) and follows the insight provided in the first letter of Paul the apostle to Timothy in the New Testament, of somewhat earlier origin, circa AD63,

"Those who want to get rich fall into temptation and a trap and into many foolish and harmful desires that plunge people into ruin and destruction. For the love of money is a root of all kinds of evil. Some people, eager for money, have wandered from the faith and pierced themselves with many griefs." (Holy Bible NIV translation 1 Timothy 6:10, 2011)

The alternative course of action might be retrenchment, when a bubble appears to be developing, and therefore a slower more stable accumulation of wealth over time, but this appears to be a less popular option (although on balance the outcomes of this choice are possibly less extreme and so less readily observable). Equally, incentive systems seem not to reward long term prudence, but short term gain. The image that would surely bring a wry smile to most of us, is one conjured up of a trader on a busy floor trying to justify throttling back on his/her more sporty positions, because of an intuition that an asset bubble may burst...but not for some years to come. The attitude is more likely to be to *"try and ride the wave"* for as long as possible and try and time the market at the very last minute. So what motivates short term gain ahead of longer term stability? The object of this study is to demonstrate that this is not just a mere accounting or forecasting error, but that there is a fundamental motivating force at work in its core.

The paper considers that an individual is concerned that if they do not strive to keep up, so as to at least maintain relative earnings and/or status parity they will fall behind, effectively suffer a loss, they will suffer from *Status Inflation*. Furthermore, the hypothesis is that as a boom accelerates and any "slack" within the system is used up, "*low-hanging fruit*" is picked i.e. the easiest opportunities are consumed, and so the harder it is to succeed ahead of rivals with the result that greater risks must be taken at each stage at an increasing rate in order to just maintain parity. This is of course offset by the effect of an increased number of opportunities at large within a booming economy. Logic dictates that in these conditions all employees should benefit from enhanced wellbeing or increased wealth. However, there is a problem in that time is finite and the working week or year within which one must outperform in order to secure a bonus/promotion is limited for everyone.

TOURNAMENTS, CONVERGENCE AND CONSUMERISM

What is worse is the coming together of two conflicting factors. Namely, within an office/business in concentrated sector (such as banking), competing employees are motivated by contest or tournament based incentive structures ("*Rank-Order Tournaments as Optimum Labor Contracts*" Lazear and Rosen 1981), being crudely summarised as "*winner-takes-all*" schemes. At the same time, within that office and, allowing for the efficiency of markets of all forms, they are afforded access to the same or similar information (such as Bloomberg/Reuters terminals and proprietorial trading platforms, the Financial Times and so on); have similar levels of experience; have similar levels of motivation; and have similar levels of education (such as Oxbridge or Russell Group graduates, "*Adverse Selection...all workers prefer to work in firms with the best workers (the major leagues)...*" Lazear and Rosen 1981).

In other words they are incentivised to exceed each other's performance, yet are made homogenous by the system, that is to say they have the same ability and tools to do the job, within the strait-jacket of a finite amount of time. In this environment, employees must think creatively, *"what will give me the edge?"* combined with the concealed knowledge that, there just isn't enough time to get into work any earlier or stay any later and squeeze in a couple of hours sleep as well. The options become increasingly limited, networks become increasingly important, but everyone has the same or similar networks, so the inside tip becomes more important - and there it is, done, line crossed. The homogeneity created by an efficient system essentially provides an increased incentive and environment to *"cheat"* the system. Acting almost as a negative externality attributed to a more general convergence theory (Abramovitz 1986). It is not just in banking or just in the UK, consider the subprime mortgage market in the USA or the Chinese milk dealers Zhang Yujun and Geng Jinping who were executed for

"endangering public safety by dangerous means, for selling more than 770 tonnes of...milk containing melamine to the now-bankrupt Sanlu Group and other dairies." (BBC 2009)

Even education is not immune (and may provide and insight as to where problems in the finance sector begin),

"...there is no doubt that the ethos of some MBA programmes is part of the problem rather than the solution. The high-octane, risk-taking, money-chasing approach favoured by some graduates may have contributed to overreach of many firms in the run up to 2008. There is some evidence that business school students become less ethical in their outlook and behaviour during the course of their studies (Broughton P 2008). Graduates of business school are more likely to cheat (Bradshaw D 2006). Education corrupts; business education corrupts absolutely." (Reeves and Knell 2009)

The sentiment is further supported,

"MBA students are the biggest cheats of all graduate students, with 56 per cent admitting to misdemeanours such as using crib notes in exams, plagiarism and downloading essays from the internet. The statistic comes from a survey of graduate students to be published in the Academy of Management Learning and Education journal. The report is based on data from about 5,300 survey respondents at 54 colleges and universities in the US and Canada, including 623 students in 32 graduate business programmes. The report will be unpleasant reading to US business schools, many of which are still smarting from the involvement of their alumni in recent corporate scandals: Jeffrey Skilling, former chief executive of Enron, received his MBA from Harvard Business School in 1979, for example. As a result, many of the top US business schools have scrambled to introduce compulsory courses on ethical behaviour at the core of their MBA programmes." (Bradshaw D 2006)

Worthy of consideration is whether the capitalist system in effect mirrors the communist system (each of which of course reviles the other) when it comes to the deliberate or accidental limiting of individuals ability to differentiate freely and therefore promotes corruption in both cases.

What this paper also espouses as significant are the feedback mechanisms of friendship circles, newspapers, television news, trade publications, and particularly advertising (that often promote the lifestyle as much as the product), which can cause individuals to feel as though they are losing-out or falling behind, even if they are not in reality (which is idea proposed in Alan de Botton's 2004 book "*Status Anxiety*").

Consumerism

This is further reinforced by the 2002 Adam Curtis documentary "Century of the Self" that identifies, with a cold eye, the reasons for the development and subsequent birth of "Consumerism". Based in part on the work of Mazur 1927, 1928, 1955 and 1965 consumerism was deliberately developed, according to Curtis, by western governments in the post-second world war period (consulting with Sigmund Freud and later Edward Bernays, his nephew) in order to ease the introduction of partial curtailments of political freedoms. It had been decided that the redrawing of election processes (particularly at party level), was necessary as a counter measure to the possibility of a future Hitler – "*people*" who, it transpired and, contrary to previous wisdom, could not in fact be trusted en-masse to vote for the "*right man*". Defeat of the Nazis had not only come at huge cost, but it had brought to the attention of the working class that if they had fought and died equally for their country, they certainly deserved an equal right to comfort and to express themselves, thus threatening the status quo and the old hierarchical order, as did the spectre of widespread unemployment. Politicians realised that these socially emancipated men needed work and that they could, if employed, also become consumers of the goods produced. More consumption meant, more employment, which meant more consumption. Now if individuals could be persuaded to express themselves through their purchases (rather than making acquisitions purely on the basis of functionality) they would not only drive demand for goods, but they would also not concern themselves with changes to political processes.

Today, we not only have these, but interactive voting on TV shows, in which

"A prematurely grey soul singer from Alabama who was once likened to a drunken dad at a wedding triumphed in the American Idol finale, which drew more votes than have ever been cast for a president in a US election. Taylor Hicks, 29, emerged as the winner in the finale of the TV show on Wednesday night in which 63m votes were cast. It is the biggest single voting night in the five-season history of the show. In the 1984 US presidential election, 54.5 million voters backed Ronald Reagan - the most votes obtained by a president." (Guardian 2006).

This slightly extend review of consumerism is important because it creates an environment in which relative status, comparison and personal image are significant. These factors in turn drive a desire for consumption, which in turn drives the desire to earn more to facilitate the consumption.

PROSPECT THEORY

All of the influences and mechanisms mentioned previously are combined with our reaction to loss, alluded to earlier, or our *"loss aversion"* (in this case loss of *status*). This essentially states that we *"hate to lose more than we love to win"* (a quote widely attributed to the tennis player Jimmy Connors), typically to the tune of approximately 2:1, i.e. I will stake twice as much to win back what I've lost than I would have staked to win a prize in the first instance (*"Prospect Theory: An Analysis of Decision Under Risk"* the seminal work by Kahneman and Tversky 1979). Kahneman and Tversky also use this to explain why the last race of the day often attracts the highest betting activity, regardless of the quality of the field – people are desperate to make up what they have lost. The motivational force of real or imagined loss within a tournament based system should logically therefore be very strong, in fact, approximately twice as strong as the desire to win the prize of a bonus or promotion in the first place (did those that designed these powerful incentive schemes take this into account when they designed them?).

ENTITLEMENT AND ENDOWMENTS

The forgoing factors start from a sense of entitlement (Pedersen 2009), born from endowments (earned or bequeathed), which in a similar way to the *loss aversion* established in *Prospect Theory*, gain greater value once endowed than would otherwise be attributed to them ("*Toward a positive theory of consumer choice*" Thaler 1980 and "*Experimental Tests of the Endowment Effect and the Coase Theorem*": Kahneman, Knetsch, and Thaler 1990). The logical progression is that if an endowment's relative value is eroded, along with the accompanying sense of entitlement, by others catching up or overtaking the individual's relative position (particularly if their catch up in unearned), it potentially creates a feeling of place being encroached upon or status being lost.

In this instance those bequeathed endowments might include: family name/inherited status; home environment (house, garden, swimming pool, the yacht, even staff; toys, clothes, holidays, the make of car that dropped a child off at school.

In addition, we add or gain our own earned endowments (that are effectively "status queues" that we consider worthy of status), such as: age, seniority, experience, graduate or professional education, sporting/academic achievements, club memberships, and wealth (although apart from the members of the "*The Sunday Times Rich List*" an individual's actual wealth is rarely observed; it is what exhibited wealth buys that can be observed).

IDENTITY THEORY

The lid on the pot of this potent "carrot and stick" brew, that potentially promotes questionable melioration, is that few of us like to break from social convention according to *Identity Theory* (Akerlof and Kranton 2000). Under group circumstances, individuals will tend not question or deviate from the in-group norm for fear of being ostracised as a "maverick", while conformity (or group reaffirming behaviour) strengthens the in-group identity and the sense of belonging. As individuals tend to have an inbuilt, prehistoric disposition towards safety, membership of *the* in-group is important, especially as much of the in-group behaviours reflect social class and or standing. Therefore, the chance that any single individual is going to "buck the system" that is already in-play (and probably was before they were hired) within their employer's operation is unlikely, particularly when they may be just one employee out of thousands (and therefore feel relatively powerless).

OTHER FACTORS

Game Theory

Other lesser factors at play, such as "Game Theory" from which "gaming the system" comes, the weighing up of the chances of getting caught-out (and/or the severity of punishment therein), the partial shield of shared-culpability, against the relative value of a hefty bonus or promotion ("Theory of Games and Economic Behaviour": Von Neumann and Morgenstern 1944 and "Non-cooperative" Games: Nash J 1950).

Homophily

Equally, there may be elements of "homophily" (Carrarini, Jackson and Pin 2009), simply put as "similarity breeds connection", but also refers to the punishment metered out for poor behaviour within the in-group against members of the in-group (similar to Identity Theory).

Hot Hand Phenomenon and Gambler's Fallacy

Also, elements of "Hot-Hand Phenomenon" (that "someone is on a roll" or "that the market is on a roll") or "Gambler's Fallacy" (that "someone's had such a bad run of luck it is bound to change next play") may exist. At the centre of both of these beliefs, is the misunderstanding/incorrect weighing-up of probabilities (primarily due to the *law of small numbers*, Kahneman and Tversky 1971).

STATUS INFLATION AS A NORMATIVE MODEL

As far as the theory of Status Inflation is concerned it emerged from logical analysis, as with Tversky and Kahneman 1986 paper on the modern theory of decision making under risk that emerged

"...from a logical analysis of games of chance rather than from a psychological analysis of risk and value. The theory was conceived as a normative model of an idealized decision maker, not as a description of the behaviour of real people. In Schumpeter's words, it "has a much better claim to being called a logic of choice than a psychology of value". The use of normative analysis to predict and explain actual behaviour is defended by several arguments. First, people are generally thought to be successful in pursuing their goals, particularly when they have incentives and opportunities to learn from experience. It seems reasonable then, to describe choice as a maximisation process. Second, competition favors rational individuals and organisations. Optimal decisions increase the chances of survival in a competitive environment, and a minority of rational individuals can sometimes impose rationality on the whole market. Third, the intuitive appeal of the axioms of rational choice makes it plausible that theory derived from these axioms should provide an acceptable account of choice behaviour. The thesis of the present article is that, in spite of these a priori arguments, the logic of choice does not provide an adequate foundation for a descriptive theory of decision making...[they go on to argue]...that the deviations of actual behaviour from the normative model are too widespread to be ignored, too systematic to be dismissed as random error, and too fundamental to be accommodated by relaxing the normative system." (Tversky and Kahneman 1986).

In order to test the theory a treatment has been devised known as "The Loan Game", which is a new experiment designed and developed by the author for the specific purpose of conducting this analysis, the details of which are provided later in the paper.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Of particular significance to this study are the topics listed below, which will be explored a little further to provide a fuller picture of the relevant literature:

1. **Status** – an overview;
2. **Tournament or Contest Theory** (*"Rank-Order Tournaments as Optimum Labor Contracts"*, Lazear and Rosen 1981); and
3. **Prospect Theory** (*"Prospect Theory: An Analysis of Decision under Risk"*, Kahneman and Tversky 1979);
4. **Internalities and Melioration** (*"Utility maximization and melioration: Internalities in individual choice"*, Herrnstein et al 1993);
5. **Endowment Effect** (*"Toward a positive theory of consumer choice"* Thaler 1980; plus *"Anomalies: The Endowment Effect, Loss Aversion, and Status Quo Bias"*, Kahneman, Knetsch, and Thaler 1990);
6. as well as a number of lesser subjects including, **Identity Theory** (*"Economics and Identity"*, Akerlof and Kranton 2000); **Homophily** (*"An Economic Model of Friendship: Homophily, Minorities, and Segregation"*, Currarini, Jackson and Pin 2009); and Hot-Hand Phenomenon and Gambler's Fallacy mentioned at the end of the previous chapter.

Firstly, as the study overlaps several areas of literature and in order to make the study practicable the selected literature is mainly focused on behavioural economics and touches on some limited elements of psychology. In addition and for the sake of brevity, certain elements of economic theory that are fundamental to full understanding of the subject are taken as read, most notably:

- i) The Standard Model (Rationality);
- ii) Game Theory and Nash Equilibrium.

However for the sake of clarity, this paper considers the theory on the assumptions of Behavioural Game Theory rather than Standard Game Theory.

Standard Game Theory hinges on four main assumptions that separate it from Behavioural Game Theory according to Wilkinson and Klaes (2012), these assumptions are highlighted in the following table:

	Standard Game Theory	Behavioural Game Theory
i)	Players have correct mental representations of the game	<i>Representation</i> – players do <u>not</u> necessarily perceive the game correctly or have incomplete representation
ii)	They have unbounded rationality	<i>Initial Conditions</i> – rationality is <i>bounded</i> through cognitive ability limitations or errors caused by <i>noise</i> (unwanted information that interferes with intended signals)
iii)	Equilibriums are reached immediately (with no time lags due to learning)	<i>Learning</i> – players learn from theirs and others payoff strategies
iv)	People are motivated by purely self-interest	<i>Social Preferences</i> – players preferences effect themselves and others, and so the distribution of payoffs

STATUS

Analysis of pure Status has been explored in several papers over many years and that "neoclassical economic theory assumes that an agent's utility depends solely on the absolute level of personal consumption. An alternative assumption, that utility or happiness depends at least in part on the comparison of one's own consumption to that of others, dates back at least to Thorstein Veblen's seminal work of 1899" (Hopkin and Kornienko 2004)

However, much of this literature focused on the comparison between money and status, the significance of status, categorising status, and its motivating power in a wholly positive frame. This differs from this study in that, here we are interested in the possibility of negative outcomes that result from the influence of relative status upon tournament based incentive schemes, caused in part by a sense of loss and that remain unchallenged due to group norming or conforming behaviours. All however note that status is a significant motivating force.

In summary, Moldovanu et al (2007) explore the significance of status and its use in the design of optimal organisational structure, for the purposes of maximising output of employees. In their work, they choose to categorise status into various levels (the top being the chief executive/leader) and look at these levels of status in the context of monetary reward and ability of candidates. Their conclusions, aside from their observation of the fact that relative status is a zero sum game (as one individual's status increases another's is reduced), is that: the top level of status can only contain a single individual (the CEO); that adding elements to status levels (classes) can reduce output; and proliferation of status classes (where each individual has their own slot) is preferable, as opposed to *"coarse partitions where it is optimal to have a wider range of performances bunched together in the same category"* (Moldovanu et al 2007); and finally, that when money is introduced to their model as a means of inducing status, it is best to have status divided into two categories where the top tier earn considerably more than the lower tier. In more general terms they consider that *"in real-life situation status is only partly determined by measureable differences in monetary compensation"* (Moldovanu et al 2007).

Usefully, Hopkins and Kornienko (2004) explore the idea that if happiness is derived (in part) from conspicuous consumption that places one ahead of another, then this creates inefficiencies in consumption, not least of all because these purchases are influenced and effected by the purchases of others. Their exploration view status from the perspective of income distribution, and interestingly, in the context of non-top tier earners (of Moldovanu et al 2007), as well as the notion of convergence mentioned previously in the introduction, they (Hopkins and Kornienko 2004) *"find that the poor are made worse off by greater equality. Such an increase in equality will also increase conspicuous waste by those on middle incomes or low and middle incomes, while conspicuous consumption by the rich may decrease. Consequently, when we consider corrective taxes on conspicuous consumption, we find that the more equally income is distributed, the higher taxes and subsidies should be for those with low to middle incomes, and the lower they should be for those with high incomes."* Their work is however of less significance to this study beyond these observations.

However, Luttmer's paper *"Neighbors as Negatives: Relative Earnings and Well-Being"* (2005), in which he examines *"whether individuals feel worse off when others around them earn more...and does "lagging behind the Joneses" diminish well-being?"* In this work Luttmer uses various factors to identify an individual's wellbeing and measures this relative to income of their neighbours. In support of this paper's assertion, he demonstrates *"that individuals' self-reported happiness is negatively affected by the earnings of others in their area...[furthermore]...an increase in neighbors' earnings and a similarly sized decrease in own income each have roughly about the same negative effect on well-being. This suggests that an increase in own income leads to a negative externality on neighbors' well-being that is of the same order of magnitude as the positive effects on own well-being."* Luttmer goes on to suggest that this therefore has implications with regard to *"optimal income taxation, consumption taxation, and residential sorting policies"*, which also go beyond the scope of this study.

Becker et al (2005) expand the study of status into the effects on risk-taking behaviour. What they note is that status and consumption are *"strong complements in the sense that greater status raises the marginal utility of other consumption."* In their model, they create a market for status positions and show that *"if the initial functional distribution of income is sufficiently compact, then the equilibrium distribution of income and the equilibrium covariance of consumption and status are the same for all initial income distributions within the "compact" range...[and]...that the result also follows when status is acquired only indirectly through the purchase of status goods."* They go on to consider this in the context of income distributions in society and further show that *"the assumption of risk taking and lotteries to acquire higher status and higher incomes leads to predictions about the distribution of income that might explain both differences and similarities in income distributions among societies, and over time within the same society. This suggests that choice and risk taking are crucial ingredients of the observed distributions of income and status."* (Becker et al 2005). This is supportive of status inflation and risk taking by individuals within the firm.

Also of significance is the work of Arthur Robson (1992) in *"Status, the Distribution of Wealth, Private and Social Attitudes to Risk."* In his work Robson suggests that *"an individual cares about his/her own wealth not only directly but also via the relative standing that this wealth induces,...[as well as]...deriving the consequences of such valuation of status for risk taking"* through conducting a revised study of Friedman and Savage (1948) *"that individuals may simultaneously purchase insurance and participate in lotteries."* He differs from this study in that his assertion is that status increases with increases in wealth more rapidly than it decreases with a loss of income, consistent with the *"concave-convex-concave"* utility function. What is of particular importance here is the notion of *"stable wealth distribution"* in which, *"all free fair gambles are rejected. It is shown that an equal distribution of wealth can never be a stable wealth distribution"* and as such is Pareto inefficient and therefore that Status is an externality. Robson's work is more focused in taxation/subsidy policy rather than in-firm behaviours.

CONTEST (TOURNAMENT) THEORY

Intuition

The problem of remunerating employees for their efforts in a way that derives maximum output has long been an issue for employers. Traditionally, piece rates, namely a payment for each completed unit of output (that meets a predetermined specification through implicit or explicit contracts), have been favoured as the optimal, efficient structure (from an economic perspective). Under this straight forward system (its simplicity being one of its attractions), the harder a worker works, the more they earn - at equilibrium a worker is paid his marginal productivity. Piece rates may only be used where the output of an employee may be easily specified and measured and has been used effectively in agriculture or manufacturing, where quality and quantity may be easily determined. However, in the modern diversified economy, there are many functions carried out that cannot be easily measured in terms of a quantifiable output (quality, quantity or both), potentially due to the complexity, duration or the collective nature of the process or a product's development and assembly. How does an employer derive maximum efficiency of production of complex outputs? Tournaments provide a solution.

The key principal behind tournaments as a method of deriving that efficiency is rewarding workers on the basis of relative performance rather than absolute performance. The notion was first explored in economic terms by Lazear and Rosen (1981), credited with the invention of the theory, in a paper entitled "*Rank-Order Tournaments as Optimum Labor Contracts*".

The Model

Workers: j and k , both strive for rewards: Large W (often presented as getting to be CEO) or small w (presented as failing to get the top job), where $W > w$. The worker who produces largest output q receives W . Output q_j is produced by effort, $\mu_j + \epsilon_j$ (random factors outside j 's control). $C(\mu)$ is a worker's effort times their skill C . C that could represent, say graduate school, is presumed to have been invested in before playing and therefore their net income is pay minus effort (held to be symmetrical between workers). There is no collusion allowed in this model. The

utility function of taking part for each worker is the probability, P (of gaining W or w , which sum to equal 1), P is equal to $g(\mu_j + \mu_k)$, where g is the function of, so $PW + (1-P)w - C(\mu)$ i.e. the probability of gaining W plus the probability of gaining w less the effort times their skill. The worker j 's reaction function is $(W-w)g(\mu_j - \mu_k) - C'(\mu_j) = 0$ and K 's reaction function is symmetrical to this. Workers simultaneously set their own input μ to maximise expected utility from playing. The Nash Equilibrium of the game is $\mu_j = \mu_k$ and the outcome of the game is $P=g(0)=0.5$, a 50/50 probability. Substituting $\mu_j = \mu_k$ we get $C'(\mu_i) = (W-w)g(0)$, where $i = j, k$. The spread between W and w determines the amount workers invest in skills before entering the game, where entry is determined by the level of prizes (the payoff for effort and investment in skills). The firm's net income is total revenue, V less cost of production, $(q_j+q_k)V = W+w$ (marginal revenue = marginal cost in equilibrium). In equilibrium, effort levels are equal, so zero profit is $V\mu = \frac{(W+w)}{2}$ which with substitution means $V\mu - C(\mu)$ is the expected worker's optimum utility and therefore the firm should seek to alter W and w to maximise $V\mu - C(\mu)$. So the firm's marginal cost of investment = it's marginal social return $V = C'(\mu)$, which in turn implies tournaments are efficient (and by the same argument can be said to allocate resources in the same way as piece rates). To this model is introduced agency theory where W is a big bonus or promotion, so that $W = V\mu - C'(\mu)/2g(0) = V\mu + V/2g(0)$ and therefore $w = V\mu + V/2g(0)$ where $V/2g(0)$ is effectively an entrance fee paid. The winning and losing prizes pay the marginal value product +/- the entrance fee. In turn this means that workers receive payment for their output/production, plus the cost of the entrance fee subject to a winner-takes-all gamble. Therefore the incentive for workers to invest in extra effort (above the marginal level) is created by the chance of the larger payoff. Therefore workers work harder in the hope that they will receive a larger payoff/promotion.

Conclusion

Top level executives are paid more, not because they are more productive per se, but in order to encourage more junior workers to employ maximum effort in order to ultimately gain the more senior position. The employee's success is of course subject to the effort they put in and skills they possess and have invested in (prior to commencing employment, a *free* and added benefit to the employer), which are weighed against the likelihood of achieving the end goal. The essence of tournaments is that workers aspire to get to the top because of the relative pay and benefit they observe that accompany that position. Tournaments have proven to be a highly effective mechanism for deriving maximum effort from employees, as demonstrated by the large volume of empirical studies e.g.

"...wages based upon rank induce the same efficient allocation of resources as an incentive reward scheme based on individual output levels..." (Lazear and Rosen 1981)

"...A key implication of tournament theory, which differs considerably from theories of efficiency wages and fairness, is that managerial pay differentials provide useful incentives to improve corporate performance." (Eriksson 1999)

Although, the findings are not unanimous,

"...the variation in executive team pay has little role in determining company performance." (Conyon et al 2001)

What is more, some environments are better suited to this approach, particularly where diligence is required especially in roles where outputs may vary subject to forces beyond the control of the employee. However, contest theory dictates that in such circumstances, in order to be effective, the disparity in payoffs (and therefore the increase in the relative value of the bonus/promotion) needs to be increased in order to provide a sufficient incentive. If there is too much volatility that is outside the control of the employee, they will reduce expenditure of effort as the return is more heavily weighted on chance outcomes and less on skill or effort. Furthermore, some employees may find it of greater benefit to invest more effort in gaming the system and sabotage of their competitors than in working harder for the company.

PROSPECT THEORY AND RISK AVERSION

Intuition

The normative model of rational choice decision making under risk has traditionally been associated with Expected Utility Theory. In 1979 Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky explored situations when the traditional axioms of Expected Utility Theory were violated and provided an alternative model "*Prospect Theory*" to explain the outcomes ("*Prospect Theory: An Analysis of Decision under Risk*" Kahneman and Tversky 1979). Prospect Theory provides an alternative view of choice,

"in which value is assigned to gains and losses rather than to final assets and in which probabilities are replaced by decision weights." (Kahneman and Tversky 1979)

Those weights tend to be lower than the corresponding probability, apart from with low probabilities, which are overweighted, which may account for why people take out insurance and/or gamble. In general terms, individuals

"underweight outcomes that are merely probable in comparison with outcomes that are obtained with certainty... This tendency, called the certainty effect, contributes to risk aversion in choices involving sure gains and risk seeking in choices involving sure losses. In addition, people generally discard components that are shared by all prospects under consideration... called the isolation effect... [that]... leads to inconsistent preferences when the same choice is presented in different forms" (Kahneman and Tversky 1979)

Model/Experiments

Decision making under risk can be considered as the making of choices between gambles...or "*Prospects*", hence Prospect Theory summarised as $(x,p;0,1-p)$ or the chance of x with the probability p .

Under Expected Utility Theory "*choices between prospects are based on the following three tenets:*

- i) *Expectation: $U(X_1, P_1; \dots; X_n, P_n) = p_1 u(x_1) + \dots + P_n U(X_n)$*
- ii) *Asset Integration: $(x_i, P_i; \dots; X_n, P)$ is acceptable at asset position w if $U(w + x_1, p_1; \dots; w + X_n, P_n) > u(w)$.*
- iii) *Risk Aversion: u is concave ($u'' < 0$)...*

But, violations can occur...

Certainty

The certainty effect is elegantly illustrated by Kahneman and Tversky's simplified version of Maurice Allais (1953) experiment (the *Allais Paradox*) in which participants were offered the following choices:

- A) Which pays out as follows:
 - i. 2,500 with a probability of 0.33
 - ii. 2,400 with a probability of 0.66
 - iii. 0 with a probability of 0.1
- B) Which pays out 2,400 with certainty

Of the 72 respondents that answered the question 18% selected A) whilst 82% selected B). They then conducted a second experiment, where subjects were presented with the choice of C) or D):

- C) Which pays out as follows:
 - i. 2,500 with a probability of 0.33
 - ii. 0 with a probability of 0.67
- D) Which pays out:
 - i. 2,400 with a probability of 0.34
 - ii. 0 with a probability of 0.66

Of the 72 respondents 83% chose C) while 17% chose D). The results are considered statistically significant at the 1% level and represent a violation of expected utility theory that predicts that an individual who is risk averse and selects B) in the first experiment should also choose D) as it represents the same pay-out as in the first game, but at a lower level of risk than choice C). However, here we can see that the potential gain of 2,500 in choice C) is weighed more highly even though the chances of receiving this pay off are lower than D).

Reflection

The experiments then progressed to situations where instead of choices involving gains or zero gains, the possibility of losses was introduced (*negative prospects*). In a series of experiments gains were replicated in a mirror image involving losses, described as the *Reflection Effect*. For example chose A) or B) where:

- A) Payoff is 4,000 with probability 0.80 or
- B) Payoff is 3,000 with probability 1.0

Compared to:

- A) Payoff is -4,000 with probability 0.80 or
- B) Payoff is -3,000 with probability 1.0

In the first of these two games 80% of respondents selected B), but in the second game (the mirror image, but using negative/loss inducing figures) only 8% selected B). This outcome is a complete reversal of choices from only 20% of people willing to take the risk in the first game (where they only stand a chance of winning), to 92% of players who were willing to take the uncertain choice in the second game, despite the fact that the potential loss was 1,000 (+33%) greater than the certain loss. This was repeated in 'Problem 4' with the odds adjusted as follows:

- A) Payoff is 4,000 with probability 0.20 or
- B) Payoff is 3,000 with probability 0.25

Compared to:

- A) Payoff is -4,000 with probability 0.20 or
- B) Payoff is -3,000 with probability 0.25

With the 95 respondents reporting:

Choice	A) 4,000 x 0.20	B) 3,000 x 0.25	A) -4,000 x 0.20	B) -3,000 x 0.25
Respondents (%)	65%	35%	42%	58%

In foregoing scenario players showed a preference for the gamble A) with potentially higher gains at lower probability in the first game, but gamble B) with smaller loses at higher probability in the second. This further highlights the inconsistencies between choices and risk aversion under uncertainty.

Isolation

Kahneman and Tversky went on to explore the effects in greater detail (including looking at *Probabilistic Insurance*) and found that their results were consistent. They then went further, looking at the Isolation Effect, where they suggest that

"in order to simplify the choice between alternatives, people often disregard components that the alternatives share, and focus on the components that distinguish them. This approach to choice problems may produce inconsistent preferences, because a pair of prospects can be decomposed into common and distinctive components in more than one way, and different decompositions sometimes lead to different preferences...the isolation effect." (Kahneman and Tversky 1979)

The isolation effect was illustrated by 'Problem 10' in the series of experiments, which was a two-stage game. The choices of both stages of the game had to be made before the game is played.

The choices were as follows:

Stage i): 0.75 probability the game ends at stage i) and 0.25 probability that the game continues to stage ii)

Stage ii): if the second stage is reached a choice of 4,000 with 0.80 probability or 3,000 with 1.0 probability.

The choice if calculated logically is between 4,000 at probability of $0.25 \times 0.80 = 0.20$ or 3,000 at probability $0.25 \times 1.0 = 0.25$. The probabilities in this scenario are the same as those in 'Problem 4', but where the preference in 'Problem 4' was for 4,000 at probability 0.20, here the preference (78% of respondents) shifted to 3,000 at probability 0.25. This suggests that players ignored the first round/stage of the game and its effect on probability and merely considered the payoffs and odds as $4,000 \times 0.80$ or $3,000 \times 1.0$. They had discounted what was common.

'PROBLEM 10'		
Choice	A) $4,000 \times 0.20$ ($0.25 \times 0.80=0.2$)	B) $3,000 \times 0.25$ ($0.25 \times 1.0=0.25$)
Respondents (%)	22%	78%
'PROBLEM 4'		
Choice	A) $4,000 \times 0.20$	B) $3,000 \times 0.25$
Respondents (%)	65%	35%

Conclusion

In summary, Kahneman and Tversky considered that decisions made in the context of uncertainty are merely choices between gambles (prospects). Expected utility theory suggests that the choices are governed by three factors, expectation (the benefit of a gamble is equal to the expected benefit of its outcome), asset integration (that any gain achieved through the gamble is added/integrated with one's existing assets and there is therefore a net gain – final assets matter), and risk aversion (the utility curve is concave, in other words a normal person prefers a certain choice over an uncertain choice that potentially yields the same value). In their experimental studies, Kahneman and Tversky tested this theory of expected utility as described and found that there were violations. The experiments were conducted using academic rigour and various controls (such as being played anonymously, with "no correct" answer, at different universities in different countries and so on), however being a laboratory experiment it could not hope to exactly replicate real world outcomes.

The conclusions of the experiments, suggested the existence of: *Coding* (people weigh up choices in terms of gains and losses, not in final net benefit/loss terms); *Combination* ("prospects can be simplified by combining the probabilities associated with identical outcomes"); *Segregation* ("some prospects contain a riskless component that is segregated from the risky component"); and *Cancellation* (the isolation effect). (Kahneman and Tversky 1979)

In addition to the main discoveries of the 1979 paper, Kahneman and Tversky suggested that there were two other factors at work that they observed, namely:

- i) Simplification – probabilities and payoffs can be rounded, with their example of 101×0.49 being *recoded* to a 50/50 chance of winning 100 (what is particularly significant in this context is the discarding of extremely unlikely occurrence);

- ii) Dominance – is a continuation on from initial simplification, whereby an ‘editing’ of the choices is conducted and with a dominant alternatives being established and all others discarded with no further investigation. Their example of such action in choices is between 500 x 0.20 or 101 x 0.49 as a choice 1, compared to choice 2 of 500 x 0.15 or 99 x 0.51. It is their suggestion that the second alternative in both choices 1 and 2 might typically be simplified to 100 x 0.50, and subsequently choice 1 (500 x 0.20) will dominate choice 2 (500 x 0.15).

They further determined that the value function (in the context of utility) was not as suggested by expected utility theory (based on final states), but more complicated and based on gains and losses in wealth or welfare. Their notion is condensed as follows:

“the value function is i) defined on deviations from the reference point; ii) generally concave for gains and commonly convex for losses; iii) steeper for losses than gains...note that the proposed S-shaped value function is steepest at the reference point, in marked contrast to the utility function postulated by Markowitz...which is relatively shallow at that region”

Figure 1 S-shaped Value Function

They further go on to talk about the weighting function, which in essence make allowance for a person’s beliefs in terms of their expectation of the probability of an outcome (consistent with the Ramsey-Savage approach as discussed by Ellsberg 1961).

INTERNALITIES

Intuition

Following the joint and individual work of Kahneman, Thaler, Tversky over several years regarding violations of the rational choice axioms, Herrnstein, Loewenstein, Prelec and Vaughan Jr's (1993) extended the study of melioration and suboptimal decision making. Melioration is defined by Herrnstein and Vaughan (1980) as,

"Melioration refers to the process of choosing that alternative among a set of alternatives which has the currently higher yield in utility. The process, as observed, is often characterized by a failure to take into account the effect of current choices on future yields. Melioration can thus be thought of as involving a within-person externality, or 'internality', which occurs when a person underweighs or ignores a consequence of his or her own behavior for him- or herself. The internality can occur for a variety of reasons: lack of awareness of the consequence, ignorance about how to respond to it, or a motivational downgrading of time deferred or otherwise obscure consequences of action." (Herrnstein et al 1993)

Furthermore, the paper asks the reader to consider an individual with a hypothetical diet of only hamburgers and caviar, both of which are provided freely. It is assumed that the desire for hamburgers is constant throughout, but that the desire for caviar diminishes as more caviar is consumed. Therefore

"In choosing between the two foods, a maximizing consumer should take account not only of the current utility of each but also of the negative impact of current caviar consumption on utility from future caviar consumption. At equilibrium the maximizer should self-ration caviar so that the current utility from caviar consumption is always greater than that from hamburger, to balance off the loss in future utility (whether discounted or not) associated with current caviar consumption." (Herrnstein et al 1993)

However, the meliorator does not ration caviar consumption, but instead consumes it until on average it provides the same utility as hamburgers and therefore any differential between the two and therefore any additional utility is eroded and lost.

The Herrnstein et al (1993) paper provides a convenient example of a workaholic,

"a 'workaholic' is a person who may be said to underweigh the impact of habitual extra hours of work on other aspects of life (e.g. relations with family and friends). Granting only that the high level of work creates problems, a person who underweighs these effects may allocate more time to work than called for by utility maximization. The workaholic syndrome and related suboptimalities have another distinctive feature (see Herrnstein and Prelec, 1991, 1992): As the current utility obtained from normal activities, such as time spent with family or friends, declines, the relative attractiveness of work increases. The result is a paradox attributable to melioration: the more harm the bad habit has wrought, the more likely the person is to transfer even more time and effort to it, up to the point at which the melioration equilibrium is reached."

In the status inflation setting, the opportunity to receive a larger bonus today outweighs in the meliorator employee's mind, the opportunity to receive smaller bonuses, but over a larger period of time. Strangely enough it is logical to assume that this increases the more prolonged a boom is, as the meliorator is increasingly likely to think that the bust may come (due to gambler's fallacy and economic reasoning and so on) and so is increasingly likely to take a short term view, as tomorrow the *"show may be over"*, which in turn is likely to become a self-fulfilling prophecy when replicated across the economy.

The Experiments

In summary, in the experiments (variation of reward functions, time pressure and payouts), subjects were asked to operate a "money machine" that on screen dispensed virtual coins from either a left or right hopper to the value shown on the face of the coin in cents. The subject had to depress either the right or left arrow to select, which hopper they wished to dispense a coin from. Once the coin had finished falling they could select again. They had 150 trial runs (that did not count towards their total) before a game of 400 runs, against which they were paid, commenced.

They were paid in cents for the total of the face value of all coins collected from both hoppers, with,

"Coin values depended on the proportion of times the subjects had hit one key or the other during the last N trials, where N was systematically varied in the experiment. The parameter N is...referred to as the 'averaging window'. When N is small, the average of left (right) key choices in the last N trials rapidly responds to the subject's current behavior. Thus the internality (the effect of current choices on future returns) responds rapidly to the subject's current choices and may, for this reason, be relatively easy to detect. When N is large the subject's current behavior has a small effect on the average behavior over the last N trials, so that the indirect effect of current behavior on payoffs operates more slowly and may be more difficult to detect." (Herrnstein et al 1993)

ENDOWMENT EFFECT

The 1990 work of Kahneman, Knetsch, and Thaler "Experimental Test of the endowment effect and the Coase Theorem" and subsequent 1991 paper "Anomalies: The Endowment Effect, Loss Aversion, and Status Quo Bias" provide an excellent framework for understanding endowment effects.

In the first paper, Kahneman et al note that Coase Theorem (*"that subject to income effects, the allocation of resources will be independent of the assignment of property rights when costless trades are possible...[i.e.]...entitlements do not effect value"*) does not appear to be consistent with empirical results when it comes to assets endowed to an individual. Therefore there exists a real disparity between Willingness to Pay (WTP), against Willingness to Accept (WTA) that

"far from being a mistake, reflect a genuine effect of reference position on preferences. Thaler (1980) labelled the increased value of a good to an individual when the good becomes part of the individual's endowment 'the endowment effect'. This effect is a manifestation of 'loss aversion', the generalization that losses are weighted substantially more than objectively commensurate gains" (Kahneman, Knetsch, and Thaler 1990)

The Experiments

Tests were conducted where subjects were endowed with tokens and then later with real assets and then asked to trade them or not as they wished (subject to offer prices they received).

In the experiments

"half of the subjects were endowed with a good and became potential sellers in each market; the other half of the subjects were potential buyers. Conventional economic analysis yields the simple prediction that one-half of the goods should be traded in in voluntary exchanges" (Kahneman, Knetsch, and Thaler 1990).

In the induced-value experiments (using tokens of no value beyond the experiment, but that could be exchanged for cash), versus when subjects were endowed with Cornell University mugs (valued exogenously at \$6.00) and then with ballpoint pens (with a price tag of \$3.98). When endowed with mugs and pens there were noticeably fewer trades (i.e. subjects associated higher values to their endowment – they required higher incentives to be parted from them once they held them if they were real things) at a ratio of approximately 20% compared to those for tokens and 4% for pens compared to tokens. Various variations were tested to control for price and commissions for trading, , but these had little effect; as well as misrepresentations and trading between actual goods that also showed that once endowed subjects were much less willing to part with their good.

As far as this status inflation is concerned, the suggestion is that people are endowed from birth with status (to a greater or lesser degree) and then add to this by achievements (academic, sporting) and acquisitions. Once this status is endowed they are extremely unwilling to be parted from it (not that anyone will actually remove it, but that because status is relative if others catch up its value is eroded or lessened and this represents a loss).

Also of note are the findings of "Samuelson and Zeckhauser (1988)...[and]... Hartman, Doane, and Woo" as reported by Kahneman, Knetsch and Thaler (1991) that found that the maintenance of status quo showed a significant bias. Furthermore, in the same paper, they note that with regard to loss aversion that,

"a central conclusion of the study of risky choice has been that such choices are best explained by assuming that the significant carriers of utility are not states of wealth or welfare, but changes relative to a neutral reference point. Another central result is that changes that make things worse (losses) loom larger than improvements or gains."

And importantly for this study,

"an implication of the endowment effect is that people treat opportunity costs differently than "out-of-pocket" costs. Foregone gains are less painful than perceived losses. This perception is strongly manifested in people's judgments about fair behaviour... The attitudes of the lay public about fairness, which are represented in their answers to...fairness questions, also pervade the decisions made by judges in many fields of the law. Supreme Court Justice Oliver Wendell Holmes (1897) put the principle this way: 'It is in the nature of a man's mind. A thing which you enjoyed and used as your own for a long time, whether property or opinion, takes root in your being and cannot be torn away without your resenting the act and trying to defend yourself, however you came by it. The law can ask no better justification than the deepest instincts of man.'" (Kahneman, Knetsch and Thaler 1991)

IDENTITY THEORY

Of lesser significance, but still of value and therefore worthy of mention, is the work of George Akerlof and Rachel Kranton (2000) *"Economics and Identity"* on Identity Theory. They contend that identity and its associated behaviours are significant in an economic context; it allows for apparently detrimental behaviour to be explained, and is of particular relevance to this study in that:

"People behave in ways that would be considered maladaptive or even self-destructive by those with other identities. The reason for this behaviour may be to bolster a sense of self or to salve a diminished self-image". (Akerlof and Kranton 2000)

Identity theory refers to "roles" (symbols to designate positions). People who exist within the social structure of society are named and give names to themselves and each other in terms of these roles;

"the categorization of the self as an occupant of a role, and the incorporation, into the self, of the meanings and expectations associated with that role and its performance" (Stets and Burke 2000)

This in turn gives a series of norms of behaviour that are consistent with the role an individual occupies.

In their paper Akerlof and Kranton start their inquiry into identity by taking a very simple example - gender. They point out that everyone on earth is assigned a gender from birth that carry with it a physical determinant, as well as certain expected modes of behaviour.

"Following the behavioral prescriptions for one's gender affirms one's self-image, or identity, as a 'man' or as a 'woman'. Violating the prescriptions evokes anxiety and discomfort in oneself and in others. Gender identity, then, changes the 'payoffs' from different actions" (Akerlof and Kranton 2000).

The interest to this paper is the notion that violation of the norms/prescriptions associated with a particular role (be it a banker or another role) *"causes discomfort in oneself and in others"* and therefore, logically is likely to promote maintenance of the status quo rather than challenges to it.

Akerlof and Kranton (2000) further suggest that identity-based behaviours are subject to four framework components, namely,

- i) *"people have identity-based payoffs derived from their own actions;*
- ii) *people have identity-based payoffs derived from others' actions;*
- iii) *third parties can generate persistent changes in these payoffs; and*
- iv) *some people may choose their identity, but choice may be proscribed for others."*

Importantly, the framework components suggest identity is related very much to the group setting. Akerlof and Kranton also present, as further evidence of this, the Robbers Cave Experiment, in which a number of 11-year old children, away on summer camp were segregated, for one week, into two groups, each of which developed its own norms, identities and patterns of behaviour. When the two groups were reintroduced in the second week of camp to compete in a tournament,

"the eleven-year-old equivalent of war broke out, with name-calling, stereotyping, and fighting." (Akerlof and Kranton 2000)

Notably, their suggestion is that, that **utility maximisation drives behaviour, but behaviour is driven by identity, and so utility is maximised by seeking identity enhancing behaviours**, a somewhat *"chicken and egg"* paradox.

As a result, we have various groups that gain identity and reaffirm identity from the group, some with behaviour that might be considered as detrimental:

- i) First group – payoffs from *own* actions:
 - a. Self-mutilation – of individuals (and/or their children) as an expression of identity; tattooing, self-starvation, genital mutilation are thought to be physical expressions of belonging to a particular social group;
 - b. Gender-centric occupations – a reverse-logic or contradictory expression against expectation e.g. women becoming marines (physical prowess, traditionally a male trait), men becoming nurses (care and tenderness, on the other hand, being assigned as 'female' traits); Interestingly, in work by Pierce (1995), of female lawyers questioned, they considered themselves as female, but to be a good lawyer required that they behave like men – relevant here to being a good corporate member requires acting in the interests of the corporation, not wider society, even though the individual is a member of that society;
 - c. Alumni giving – charity is not often associated with giving to the most economically efficient organisations, but to those with which we feel an association, the most extreme example being alumni giving generously to their former schools and universities;
 - d. Mountaineering – enhances and exaggerates an individual's sense of self.
- ii) Second group - payoffs from *others* actions:
 - a. Gender-centric occupations – a woman doing a 'man's' job may cause men to feel insecure, invoking a reaction that asserts 'maleness', contrary to the welfare of the woman;
 - b. Masculinity and insult – if an insult is left un-counteracted, it may impugn a man's masculinity, the 'culture-of-honour';
 - c. Changing groups or violating prescriptions – those that remain within the group feel offended and react accordingly with insults and so on, which "*distances oneself from the maverick and affirms one's own self-image*" (Akerlof and Kranton 2000); this is also seen in those who try to 'socially climb' and attract mocking and scorn (this could be argued as a counter to or equally in support of the hypothesis presented in this paper);
- iii) Third group – *choice* of identity (c_j is at least in part a choice):
 - a. Career woman or mother?; Private or state schooling for children?; sometimes however, it is more difficult to choose an alternative categorie, for example, ethnicity

- iv) Fourth group – *creation and manipulation* of social categories:
- a. Advertising – often tied with branding to make us feel differently towards a particular company or product in the context of ideals of identity;
 - b. Professional and Graduate Schools – that shape behaviour;
 - c. Political Identity – e.g. Nazis in 1930s Germany who sought to shape identity through creation of ethnic/racial divisions (see also Dennis Gansel's 2008 film 'Die Welle' or *The Wave*, a 1981 film, in turn based on a German TV series, in which students at a school form a distinct social group, motivated by in-group out of group distinctions and division)

Identity is therefore highly significant in decision-making behaviour and secondly that group context or categorisation is in turn highly significant to this identity. The evidence suggests that individuals make selections that are motivated by their identity, sometimes in violation of the assumptions of the standard model. In light of this it is distinctly possible that individuals could make decisions detrimental to wider society. In the world of banking, individuals find themselves in a group of highly competitive "go-getters", and will wish to adopt the behaviours associated with conforming to that group. If the group is taking risks, this will prompt the individual to take risks (aside from the motivation from not getting sacked for not achieving target – this is a purely identity based theory that sits on top of practical concerns such as these). Groups naturally have leaders (appointed or achieved roles) and the group takes direction from the leader, therefore it only requires a relatively small number of players to be risk seeking to create a risk-taking group norm. Individual are not likely to deviate from the group norm.

OTHER THEORIES

The Hot Hand and Gambler's Fallacy

Both the Hot Hand in basketball and the Gambler's Fallacy stem from "the belief in the law of small numbers" (Tversky and Kahneman 1971), which essentially suggests that we all tend to believe that the law of large numbers should apply in all circumstances, including within a much smaller sample. However, smaller samples tend to deviate from chance expectation, with a surfeit of alternations and a shortage of long runs that might be found in larger samples that do fulfil the expectations of chance. In other words, humans expect a fair (unbiased) coin flip to almost always reflect a distribution of outcomes equal to the 50/50 chance of a particular result, even in a short sequence. The result of this incorrect assessment is that two equally incorrect assumptions are created. Firstly, that after a run of 'heads' results that a 'tails' result is more likely and yet of course this is irrational, as the odds have not changed from being 50/50 chance. This is what has become known as the 'Gambler's Fallacy', as explored by Tversky and Kahneman in 1974. Secondly, the incorrect assessment causes individuals to reject the notion of randomness if a sequence occurs, which gives rise to the belief in the 'Hot Hand', namely that something else, some other factor must be at play to cause a deviation from the expected random sequence (Wagenaar 1972).

Homophily

The principal of homophily is related to the notion that 'birds of a feather flock together', in other words similarity of type encourages group formation and similar behaviours. The theory has been most extensively explored in network studies and is really concerned with connection between individuals.

"The network structure of social interactions influences a variety of behaviors and economic outcomes, including the formation of opinions, decisions on which products to buy, investment in education, access to jobs, and social mobility, just to name a few. The extent to which a society is segregated across different groups can be critical in determining things like how quickly information diffuses and the extent to which there is underinvestment in human capital, among other things" (Currarini et al 2009)

THE TREATMENT

3. THE TREATMENT

HYPOTHESIS

That individual risk taking behaviour within a firm is influenced by:

Endogenously:

- I) Contests/Tournaments;
- II) Loss Aversion, and actual, imagined and feared "loss" of status caused by:
 - a. Sense of Entitlement and Status derived from Endowments;
 - b. Reduction (or fear of reduction) in Relative Status caused by others "catching up";
- III) Internalities/Melioration – taking short term choices;
- IV) Misunderstanding odds/law of small numbers (gambler's fallacy, etc);
- V) Cycle is not broken/Status Quo maintained due to group norming behaviour.

Exogenously:

- i) The market movements:
 - a. Up,
 - b. Flat,
 - c. Down (crash).

In the real world other factors that might have bearing could include: an individual's personal health or that of a friend or member of the family; moral/ethical upbringing; any addictions; a criminal record; and so on *ad infinitum*.

The mathematic model would therefore be that:

Risk Taking Behaviour (B) = $f((\text{Current Social Status (Sc)} - \text{Social Status of colleagues (So)} \pm \text{Status}) + \text{unobservables})$

i.e. $B = f((Sc - So) \pm S) + \mu$

In the Loan Game social status is set to equality between individual and the peer group, $S_c - S_o = 0$, because at the beginning on a normalised social status index $S_c = 1$ and $S_o = 1$, so $1-1=0$. Furthermore, α becomes the outturn of the establishing round. Continuing, it is the relative changes in status that are significant, subject to changes in the market and outturns of gambles. Changes in status outside the experiment could be measured in many forms (bonuses, promotions, value of houses/cars or ostentatious items such as watches, mobile phone and so on)

The econometric model might be as follows:

current choice (\tilde{Y}_t) = previous choice (β_1) \pm status from previous round (β_{2t-1}) + error term (ϵ)

Here, status is measured in wealth in each round relative to the market wealth. Could Not Play results were excluded from the analysis.

The first is on the FULL experimental data (with the feedback mechanism, which should trigger emotions of "getting left behind" if Status Inflation exists) and the second is on the CONTROL experimental data (with no feedback mechanism, so that any changes can be attributed to subject "instinct" to time the market – Hot-Hand Phenomenon). The difference between the two results would be beta of Status Inflation (β_{si}).

The null hypothesis is therefore that $H_0: \beta_{si} = 0$, in other words, it has no explanatory power and therefore *Status Inflation* does not exist or is not measureable in this way.

THE 'LOAN GAME' EXPERIMENT

Introduction

The players, in pairs each fulfil two roles in the experiment:

- i) that of a loan officer in a bank; and then
- ii) as the credit committee officer (who must approve the loans of the loan officer, their neighbour in the game).

The game is played over a total of 11 periods (including an establishing phase of 1 period) equivalent to 11 years in the frame of the game. This reflects the Juglar Fixed Investment Cycle that empirically runs for 7-11 years (Juglar 1862).

The establishing period that allows players to become conversant with the game methodology and to start accumulating wealth (relative *status*). It is hoped that the accumulation and relative loss (when others gain while subjects are banned or "under-bet") of wealth/status will initiate some of the behavioural changes that will cause a deviation from the usual rational choice assumed by the standard model. Furthermore, it is hoped that the results from the game will illustrate evidence of Prospect (loss aversion) and Tournament (competitive streak to bet higher to "win big") theories at work that could be said to demonstrate the underlying theory of "Status Inflation" in this paper. In addition, it is hoped that Tournament theory will extend to efforts to "time the market", with the exhibition of Hot-Hand Phenomenon and Gambler's Fallacy.

The experiment has been designed to reflect, in simplified terms, a typical business cycle, determined exogenously by balls drawn from an opaque bag. There are three 'states-of-the-market', a 'growing' (G) economy, a 'flat-line' (F) economy and a 'crash' (C) economy. These states are determined by drawing ping pong balls of three different types from the bag, with replacement in order to maintain the odds in proportion and to better reflect correct sampling techniques. In practice the draws were conducted by subjects in order to demonstrate impartiality and create a greater sense of participation:

- i) G - growth (white balls x14 = 0.7 probability);
- ii) F - flat-line (blue balls x4 = 0.2 probability); and
- iii) C - crash (orange balls x2 = 0.1 probability).

The first period is always be set to 'growth' as part of the establishing process to allow for a risk free bet while comprehension of the game methodology. Furthermore, this encourages engagement and increase willingness to participate.

Lagging the effects of draws had been considered, but the idea was dropped as an unnecessary complication that yielded little or no useful additional information. Consequently, all draw result in an immediate effect on that period of the game, creating a very direct action and effect, which is useful in a game of relatively short (duration once initial explanations are completed, which were also simplified by this decision).

All players receive a fee for every £million earned within the game at an exchange rate of £1.00 per £million (rounded to the nearest pound). The exchange rate can be changed to suit the particular circumstances of the game. Initially, a participation fee had been proposed, but it was decided that by not offering this it would give greater motivation for the subjects to play with their optimal ability in order to maximise their reward for their time. This was also considered to be more consistent with the "winner-takes-all" notion of Tournament Theory and removed the requirement for posting of a ranking or offering a single large prize for the winner, whilst still providing an adequate incentive.

THE PLAYERS OBJECTIVE

The player, in the first instance, is the loan officer in the bank.

The aim of the player is to accrue the greatest value of personal assets, which are bought with earned bonuses, during the 11 periods of the game. There are three sort of asset:

- i) house (cost £1,000,000); earning a return of 10% per annum for the duration of the game (which is capitalised to allow calculation of final capital value);
- ii) investment bond (cost £500,000); earning 8% per annum; and a
- iii) cash deposit (cost £100,000); earning 3% per annum.

Bonuses are earned through the granting of loans at differing levels of "loan-to-value" (LTV) to new bank customers.

It is stated that potential customers approach the bank, for whom the loan officer works, for debt funding for a project.

The LTV is assumed to be the equity remaining in the project in the event of liquidation and so as the duration of loans offered is one year, it is the amount the bank has returned to it in the event of a "crash" in the market in that year.

In the event of a crash in the market no bonuses can be earned in that year.

Over leverage results in loss for the bank and loan officers who have leant recklessly are punished by the bank by being banned from lending. Naturally, the loan officer cannot earn bonuses during periods when they are banned. In the real world an employee might be sacked and the ban might be equivalent to the related reputational damage incurred that prevents them from securing another job for a period of time.

Bans are set at one year for granting of nonperforming loans of >100% to 150% and two years for those of over 150% up to the maximum of 200%. Loans of less than 100% do not incur losses for the bank and so do not attract a ban.

Loan officers are incentivised, through bonuses to attract more business to the bank. The only tool the loan officer has to attract new business to the bank is to adjust the LTV that he/she is prepared to offer. At higher LTVs the loan officer is assumed to secure more business for the bank and in turn receives higher bonuses. The intuition for this is that by offering higher LTVs the loan officer is essentially opening up the bank to a wider range/number of projects within the market.

Bonuses are set at:

- i) £1,000,000 when a G ball is drawn from the bag for that period (for the highest LTVs, between 150-200% and therefore the riskiest);
- ii) £500,000 when a G ball is drawn (mid-ranking LTVs >100%-150% and therefore loans of lower risk); and
- iii) £100,000 when a G ball is drawn (for the lowest LTVs <100% and therefore assumed to carry no risk); this is also the maximum bonus for any player regardless of LTV in the event of a F ball being drawn from the bag for that period.

The loan officer must therefore weigh the opportunity to gain bigger bonuses against the chance of a market crash (the performance of the loans is determined by the state-of-the-market as denoted by the balls draw from the bag) and potential punishment for the failure of over leveraged loans (i.e. over 100% LTV).

Bonuses earned as a result of successful loans i.e. those that do not fail in the year they are granted, are banked and assets purchased with them in previous periods are secure. This also reflects real life, where claw-back of assets currently remains the wishful thinking of politicians.

Bonuses earned must be spent in full in the year that they are earned. The bonuses correspond to the three assets that may be purchased that in turn earn the capitalised return during the game. This structure ensures that there is adequate incentive to take risks from the beginning of the game.

The scale and range of both bonuses and assets is designed to provide clear differentiation between the taking of: zero risk, moderate risk and high risk. The lack of punishment is reward for prudence, but as in real life during a boom, prudence is under rewarded in comparison to more bullish activity, which is conversely punished during a crash. However on balance the relative weights favour bullish behaviour (when the odds of a crash are 10-1), which is done deliberately in an attempt to replicate the sentiment that generally drives capitalist economies forward overall.

LTVs may only be granted (and therefore bonuses earned) subject to the approval (signoff) of the percentage amount from *Credit Committee*. The role of *Credit Committee* is the second function that the subject fulfils during the course of the game. Players sit in pairs. First each player completes the LTV amount they propose for that year in the relevant box on the "Earning Your Bonus" sheet. Players then swap "Earning Your Bonus" Sheets with their neighbour (example below with example of the completed form afterwards):

EARNING YOUR BONUS							
YOU		YOUR NEIGHBOUR		YOUR NEIGHBOUR			
Name + ID Number		Name + ID Number					
<small>to be filled in each round by Loan Officer (you)</small>		<small>filled in each round by Credit Committee (your neighbour)</small>		<small>to be filled in each round by Credit Committee Officer</small>			
LOAN OFFICER		CREDIT COMMITTEE		CREDIT COMMITTEE			
Year	loan to Value	Approved	Declined	Market Move	Bonus		
<small>(round)</small>	<small>50%-200% in 10% increments</small>	<small>sign initial in box</small>		<small>Crash = C, Flat = F, Growth = G (given by neighbour)</small>	<small>See table on the board (or below)</small>		
1	trial year	trial year	trial year	trial year	trial year		
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							
7							
8							
9							
10							
11							

SUMMARY PAYOFF TABLE												
Loan to Value	50%	100%	110%	120%	130%	140%	150%	160%	170%	180%	190%	200%
Equivalent Bonus if "G"	100,000				500,000					1,000,000		
Equivalent Bonus if "F"	100,000				100,000					100,000		
Equivalent Bonus if "C"	0				0					0		
Ban if "Crash" Ball Drawn	0				1 year					2 Years		

Figure 2 Earning Your Bonus Hand-out

EARNING YOUR BONUS				SPENDING			
YOU		YOUR NEIGHBOUR		YOUR NEIGHBOUR			
Name + ID Number	Terry 6200368	Name + ID Number	Nick 6200348				
take filled in each round by Loan Officer (you)		fill in each round by Credit Committee (your neighbour)		take filled in each round by Credit Committee Officer		to be filled in each round by Loan Officer (you)	
LOAN OFFICER		CREDIT COMMITTEE		CREDIT COMMITTEE		LOAN OFFICER	
Year	loan to Value	Approved	Declined	Market Move	Bonus	House	Loan
(round)	Risk-200k in increments	sign/initial in box		Crash - G, Flat - F, Growth - G (give by 100k/100k)	See table on the board for bonus	(\$/week)	here should only
1	50%	nick		G	100,000		1
2	1.00%	nick		G	100,000		2
3	1.10%	nick		C			3
4	1.70%	nick	nick	BRN			4
5	1.80%	nick		G	1,000,000		5 X1
6	1.40%	nick		F	100,000		6
7	1.50%	nick		F	100,000		7
8	1.50%	nick		G	500,000		8
9	1.00%			G	100,000		9
10	50%			G	100,000		10
11	1.80%			G	1,000,000		11 X1

mistakes should be crossed through with a single line and the new amount written nextdoor & signed/initialled by the credit committee

Loan to Value	50%	100%	110%	120%	130%	140%	150%	160%	170%	180%	190%	200%
Equivalent Bonus if "G"	100,000				500,000					1,000,000		
Equivalent Bonus if "F"	100,000					100,000					100,000	

Figure 3 Completed Example - Earning Your Bonus Hand-out

The neighbour then acts as Credit Committee and either agrees the LTV or not. If approval is not immediately forthcoming it is expected that there will be some negotiation between subjects in order to arrive at an agreed LTV. If however the LTV remains unapproved, then no bonus may be earned, although as subjects act both as loan officer and credit committee for each other and therefore refusal to signoff is likely to result in retaliation, it is anticipated that signoff will ultimately be achieved. There are no explicit instructions to subjects regarding this form of collusion, which is assumed as in the real world to be self-regulating. Furthermore, in the real world, bank lenders frequently sit on each other's credit committees and are implicitly expected to act in the best interests of the bank, although the reality may be that they operate within the best mutual beneficial agreement they can negotiate.

Below is the summary LTV/payoff/punishment table:

SUMMARY PAYOFF TABLE												
Loan to Value	50%	100%	110%	120%	130%	140%	150%	160%	170%	180%	190%	200%
Equivalent Bonus if "G"	100,000		500,000				1,000,000					
Equivalent Bonus if "F"	100,000		100,000				100,000					
Equivalent Bonus if "C"	0		0				0					
Ban if "Crash" Ball Drawn	0		1 year				2 Years					

Figure 4 Summary LTV Percentage & Payoff/Punishment

Once the LTV has been agreed and the state-of-the-market for that period determined by drawing of the ping pong ball, subjects discover what bonus they are entitled to. Players now enter phase two of the game "Spending Your Bonus" (which occurs in each round of the game). This is when players must "choose" how to spend their bonus, although the reality is that they have no choice at this stage, as this has already been determined by how much bonus they have earned, in other words they made their choice when they elected the LTV to lend at.

The purpose of the second phase of the game is twofold:

- i) to provide the motivation for players to take risks when they see their own performance against that of their neighbour (not so for the control group where there is no such feedback);
- ii) to provide a mechanism for calculating relative performance in the game and therefore the payoff to each subject at the end of the game; and
- iii) to provide the basis for the aggregate feedback mechanism (again this is done to replicate real life as far as is possible – in real life we do not, for the most part observe real earnings or consumption of a large number of people; instead we observe the consumption of our neighbours and friends and the aggregate consumption of the nation as presented in daily national media and trade publications; furthermore we are stimulated by advertising that directly or indirectly takes this information and distils it into the aspirational images of the products it aims to sell).

The results of the spending stage (because the decision making process has already been conducted in phase one "Earnign Your Bonus") is largely of interest to the players alone, except for the very significant comparison between the Full experiment and the control, from which we are able to determine the existence or otherwise of *Status Inflation*.

Example of the "Spending Your Bonus" form is shown below with a completed version:

SPENDING YOUR BONUS				Capital Value Appreciation Table			Capital Value Appreciation Table			
<i>to be filled in each round by Credit Committee</i>				<i>(use to help calc your annual & total wealth)</i>			<i>to be filled in by you</i>			
LOAN OFFICER				House	Investment	Cash	House	Investment	Cash	
House	Investment	Cash		annual return	annual return	annual return	(10% p.a.)	(8% p.a.)	(3% p.a.)	
(£1m each)	(£0.5m each)	(£0.1m each)		10%	8%	3%	<i>(fill in as appropriate)</i>	<i>(fill in as appropriate)</i>	<i>(fill in as appropriate)</i>	
<i>there should only be a number for each year</i>				<i>(select amount based on your and investment made)</i>			<i>there should only be a number for each year</i>			
1				1	£2,593,742	£1,079,462	£134,392	1		
2				2	£2,357,948	£999,502	£130,477	2		
3				3	£2,143,589	£925,465	£126,677	3		
4				4	£1,948,717	£856,912	£122,987	4		
5				5	£1,771,561	£793,437	£119,405	5		
6				6	£1,610,510	£734,664	£115,927	6		
7				7	£1,464,100	£680,244	£112,551	7		
8				8	£1,331,000	£629,856	£109,273	8		
9				9	£1,210,000	£583,200	£106,090	9		
10				10	£1,100,000	£540,000	£103,000	10		
11				11	£1,000,000	£500,000	£100,000	11		
				Totals						

Figure 5 Spending Your Bonus Hand-out

SPENDING YOUR BONUS				Capital Value Appreciation Table			Capital Value Appreciation Table			
<i>to be filled in each round by Credit Committee</i>				<i>(use to help calc your annual & total wealth)</i>			<i>to be filled in by you</i>			
LOAN OFFICER				House	Investment	Cash	House	Investment	Cash	
House	Investment	Cash		annual return	annual return	annual return	(10% p.a.)	(8% p.a.)	(3% p.a.)	
(£1m each)	(£0.5m each)	(£0.1m each)		10%	8%	3%	<i>(fill in as appropriate)</i>	<i>(fill in as appropriate)</i>	<i>(fill in as appropriate)</i>	
<i>there should only be a number for each year</i>				<i>(select amount based on your and investment made)</i>			<i>there should only be a number for each year</i>			
1				1	£2,593,742	£1,079,462	£134,392	1		\$134,392
2				2	£2,357,948	£999,502	£130,477	2		\$130,477
3				3	£2,143,589	£925,465	£126,677	3		
4				4	£1,948,717	£856,912	£122,987	4		
5				5	£1,771,561	£793,437	£119,405	5	\$1,771,561	
6				6	£1,610,510	£734,664	£115,927	6		\$115,927
7				7	£1,464,100	£680,244	£112,551	7		\$112,551
8				8	£1,331,000	£629,856	£109,273	8	\$629,856	
9				9	£1,210,000	£583,200	£106,090	9		\$106,090
10				10	£1,100,000	£540,000	£103,000	10		\$103,000
11				11	£1,000,000	£500,000	£100,000	11	\$1,000,000	
				Totals						
							\$2,771,561	\$629,856	\$702,437	
							Grand Total		\$ 4,103,854	

Figure 6 Completed Example - Spending Your Bonus

A full set of instructions for the assessor is provided in the appendices.

Framing

Briefly, it is worth mentioning that the anchoring effect (Thaler and Sunstein 2008) is expected to work alongside one of the menu effects, *Attraction Effect* – whilst the Cash Deposit of £0.1m is the default acquisition in a riskless decision and is a distinct decision in its own right, its low rate of return also has the effect of making the other two choices of House and Investment Bond investments look particularly attractive and thereby encourage greater risk taking (this could be said to be a 'light' version of the decoy effect). However, other menu effects such as *Preference for the Salient* – where complex choices are simplified in the mind of the consumer, is not relevant to this experiment. Equally, *Choice Avoidance*, *Momentum Effect*, *Vicarious Consumption Effect* and *Confusion* effect are not relevant to this study, although it is possible that some players may simply not grasp the purpose and structure of the game and subsequently make random choices that do not make rational sense.

Work by Della Vigna (2009) suggests that in complex situations individuals are overwhelmed and pay insufficient attention to the outcomes of decisions they make, while Frederick et al (2009) illustrates that they do not always in this state of inattention consider the alternatives thoroughly. Equally, Nordgren and Dijksterhuis (2009) suggest that excessive deliberation can have a similar effect and result in sub-optimal choices being made.

STATISTICAL EVALUATION OF RESULTS

4. EVALUATION OF RESULTS

BACKGROUND TO FINANCE AND ECONOMICS EXPERIMENTAL LABORATORY AT EXETER (FEELE)

The experiment was conducted on 13th June 2013 between 1030 and 1500 in the Finance and Economics Experimental Laboratory at Exeter (FEELE) University.

"FEELE has an existing database of active participants (approximately 1,800). These participants are undergraduate students from the University of Exeter as well as non-students. They are contacted at the beginning of each academic year and are invited to register with FEELE if they wish to participate in economics experiments.

Participants register their personal details on ORSEE, software specifically designed to optimise recruitment for economics experiments. This includes their name, gender, degree programme (if applicable), and e-mail address.

FEELE operates a strict policy on the confidentiality of the data provided by our participants. We do not share personal information on our participants with any outside parties.

The recruitment of participants is managed through ORSEE. This allows for the participant sampling for a given session, or set of sessions, to be made conditional on any characteristics relevant to the study (e.g. gender)...

...Everyone who takes part in an experiment conducted at FEELE must sign an informed consent document outlining the rules under which FEELE operates. This states: "Once the session is under way, your continuing participation is voluntary and you have the right to withdraw at any time." The consent form is publically available.

In line with University of Exeter and the British Psychological Society's ethics policies, participants are fully informed about the nature of the study that they are considering participating in (they are not, however, informed about hypotheses) and must give their informed consent prior to participating. Participants are permitted to opt out at any time with no penalty and are allowed to withdraw their data subsequent to participating.

FEELE operates under the methodological paradigm of experimental economics. This means we do not allow experiments to be conducted at FEELE which involve participant deception." (FEELE 2013)

THE EXPERIMENT

Gender, age, undergraduate/post graduate, area of study filtering criteria were deliberately left open so as to gain as true a random sample as possible. As a result there was a gender split of 14:15 (males to female) or 48.3%:51.7% across the sample as a whole. The majority of students were under graduate, aged between 18 and 25 (27/29), while 2 were older aged between 40 and 50. Approximately half were from economics or business courses and the remainder from non-business courses (arts, humanities and language departments).

The experiment was conducted in two parts:

- i) Full experiment: 16 subjects (from a response of 23);
 - a. (8 male: 8 female);
 - b. 1 post graduate;
 - c. Even mix of departments (business to non-business);
 - d. Between 1100 and 1145;
 - e. Candidates seemed alert and interested;
 - f. Candidates seemed calm;
 - g. Candidates seemed confident and reasonably extrovert (they engaged easily with each other);
 - h. Candidates appeared to grasp the methodology and gain understanding of the game quickly.
- ii) Control experiment: 13 subjects (from a response of 18);
 - a. (6 male: 7 female);
 - b. 1 post graduate;
 - c. Even mix of departments (business to non-business);
 - d. Between 1330 and 1415;
 - e. Candidates seemed less alert and less interested than the morning session;
 - f. Candidates seemed calm;
 - g. Candidates seemed less confident and less extrovert than the morning session (there was less interaction, due to game design in the control, but even so interaction between subjects was reduced);
 - h. Candidates appeared to take longer to grasp the methodology and gain understanding of the game.

The average payment was: £8.13 (equivalent to £10.85 per hour).

SUMMARY OF RESULTS

Introduction

The Loan Game generates the equivalent to Panel Data, that is to say that it is the results of a sample (cross section) of the population, over a series of 11-time periods (albeit that these are drawn on the same day, during the 45-60 minute period of the experiment). The two experiments conducted are referred to in this analysis as the FULL experiment (Group F) and the CONTROL (Group C). In addition, the data from the two groups is present in consolidated form, referred to as the Group Cons.

- i) Full experiment: Group F 16 subjects;
- ii) Control experiment: Group C 13 subjects;
- iii) Consolidated results: Group Cons 29 subjects.

29 subjects making a LTV decision in each round resulted in a total of 319 decisions, less those periods when players were subject to a ban:

- i) Group F in periods:
 - a. 5 and 6 = 23 (following a crash in period 4); and
 - b. 8 and 9 = 27 (following crashes in periods 7 and 8);
 - c. + 1 input error (only one input error was discovered in both sets of data, where a subject took an extra year prohibition when they need not have done, which was in all likelihood due to the fact that this took place in the first half of the game when learning might still be going on, but more likely due to their neighbour correctly taking a ban at this time).
- ii) Group C in periods:
 - a. 6 and 7 = 17 (following a crash in period 5);

Resulting in a total of 68 no play scenarios (described as "Z" situations) and a total of 251 active decisions for the data pool as a whole.

The analysis of the results is primarily concerned with the choices and the level of risk associated with them (all other results are as a consequence of these choices and the draws/state-of-the-market outcomes). First we consider the draws and then we look at the choices made in the context of the draws and aim to take inferences from the results as a consequence.

The draws were as follows:

Period	Full Experiment	Control Experiment	Variance
	<i>(G = growth; F = flat-line; and C= crash)</i>		
1	G	G	=
2	G	G	=
3	G	G	=
4	C	G	C : G
5	G	C	G : C
6	G	G	=
7	C	F	C : F
8	C	F	C : F
9	G	F	G : F
10	G	G	=
11	F	G	F : G
Total	7 x G	7 x G	0:0
	1 x F	3 x F	1:3
	3 x C	1 x C	3:1
(%)	G = 63.6%	G = 63.6%	0.0%
	F = 9.1%	F = 27.3%	-18.2%
	C = 27.3%	C = 9.1%	+18.2%
Expected Probabilities	G = 70.0%	G = 70.0%	0.0%
	F = 20.0%	F = 20.0%	0.0%
	C = 10.0%	C = 10.0%	0.0%
Variance <i>(expected to actual)</i>	-6.4%	-6.4%	
	-10.9%	7.3%	
	17.3%	-0.9%	

Figure 7 Summary of Draws

In the case of Group F, which suffered from three times as many crashes as forecast, one could reasonably expect a higher bonus success rate and fewer bans if the experiment was repeated on multiple occasions or with larger samples and the data showed consistency. Coincidentally, both Groups F and C had the same number of growth draws (7) as forecast, which makes drawing comparison between the two a little more meaningful (the variance occurring between crashes and flat-line draws – which, aside from potential bans, means the difference between zero bonus and a £100,000 capped bonus each time).

Of note and upon initial inspection of the data, the following results were revealed:

	# Made No Changes	% Made No Changes	# Made 1 Change	% Made 1 Change	# Remainder	% Remainder
GROUP F	1	6.3%	6	37.5%	9	56.3%
GROUP C	1	7.7%	4	30.8%	8	61.5%
GROUP Cons	2	6.9%	10	34.5%	17	58.6%

Note:

- i) *excludes first/establishing round*
- ii) *of those in GROUP F who made no changes or 1 change, they were also the pairs that copied/repeated each other's choices, excl. the single "odd-one-out" in pair #2*
- iii) *GROUP C were all independent choices*

Figure 8 Summary of Change of Choices

On the face of it, on average approximately 7 per cent of subjects (one from each group) were either disinterested in the experiment, did not understand the game or were running a system/ trying to game the system from the outset. A further 35 per cent made only one change in their choices across all periods (excluding the establishing period #1), which initially the same, but with a greater likelihood of this being down to a lack of understanding. It is difficult to determine from the data alone what the true explanation was for the lack of changes was, however interrogation of the subject feedback forms provides some insight:

In Group F, 6 of the 7, and in Group C, 3 of the 5 (or Group Cons: 9 of 12 or 75%) who made one or no changes (i.e. were suspected of running a system/trying to game the system or were disinterested) also completed feedback forms, which indicates that they were not disinterested. On closer inspection of the forms, it only two of the "one" or "no change" individuals reported any confusion/difficulty in understanding, i.e. 7 out 12 were running a system (58% of the 12 or 24% of the total sample of 29 subjects – it would be interesting in future samples whether this figure was consistent). Indeed only a further two subjects indicated any lack of understanding – regarding the range of percentage choices that made no difference to the outcome within a particular bracket, which of course is a deliberate part of the game design. Two further subjects indicated they would have like the game to have been more complex or had a wider range of payoffs.

A general comment is that in future CONTROL games, should require either the swapping of sheets for marking purposes (with an individual not directly participating in the game), or the production of a computer run version to prevent changing of choices post balls being drawn. In the case therefore of a computerised version being developed, it may also be possible to run the control in parallel with the full experiment (in a different location, but with same ball draws), and thus allow for direct comparison between groups.

Summary descriptive statistics (for all data by group, across all periods):

Statistic	GROUP F	GROUP C	GROUP Cons
MEAN	153%	172%	162%
MODE	160%	200%	160%
MEDIAN	160%	185%	160%
VARIANCE	3.6%	10.6%	8.9%
STANDARD DEVIATION	0.19	0.33	0.30
KURTOSIS	0.8	-0.4	1.6
SKEWNESS	-0.4	-0.8	-0.7

Figure 9 Summary Descriptive Statistics

On the face of the descriptive statistics, Group C appears to on average be less risk adverse, but show higher volatility of results. Group F, by contrast shows on average a lower appetite for risk, but considerably lower volatility of results. The range is obviously the same in both cases being from 50% to 200% in increments of 50% up to 100% and 10% thereafter up to 200% (plus one bin of 0% for occasions when a player is banned), giving a total of 13 bins.

Analysis of the histograms for each group illustrates how few choices were of no risk (i.e. 50% or 100%; 0% indicates a player was banned for one choice)

Figure 10 Data Histogram

On the face of the above information it would appear that (in the context of very small sample sizes and a discrete number of choices) the data is reasonably normally distributed, with a cluster of outliers in the 200% bin for the control group.

The scatter chart for the whole data set sheds little further light:

Figure 11 Scatter Chart

Summary of Frequency of choices:

<i>BIN</i>	GROUP F		GROUP C		GROUP Cons	
	Frequency	(%)	Frequency	(%)	Frequency	(%)
0%	53	30%	15	10%	68	21%
50%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
100%	0	0%	9	6%	9	3%
110%	7	4%	4	3%	11	3%
120%	8	5%	0	0%	8	3%
130%	9	5%	5	3%	14	4%
140%	4	2%	1	1%	5	2%
150%	19	11%	19	13%	38	12%
160%	63	36%	22	15%	85	27%
170%	4	2%	0	0%	4	1%
180%	5	3%	4	3%	9	3%
190%	0	0%	1	1%	1	0%
200%	4	2%	63	44%	67	21%
Other	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
	176	100%	143	100%	319	100%

Figure 12 Frequency of Choices – All Groups

Of note, there were no selections of 50% LTV and only 3% of total choices across both experiments were of 100% LTV, which suggests a general tolerance risk. Indeed the most popular choices by far were those of 160% and 200% LTVs accounting for a combined total of almost half of all choices and a further 12% of choices was accounted for by selections of 150% LTV. Between them choices between 150% and 200% accounted for almost two thirds of all choices.

The following table shows the Group F results by round and the corresponding draw for that round:

DRAWS	G	G	G	C	G	G	C	C	G	G	F	Total	%
0%	0	0	0	0	16	9	0	16	12	0	0	53	30%
50%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
100%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
110%	0	1	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	7	4%
120%	3	1	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	8	5%
130%	2	1	2	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	9	5%
140%	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	4	2%
150%	2	6	2	3	0	3	0	0	2	1	0	19	11%
160%	7	6	10	7	0	1	10	0	1	10	11	63	36%
170%	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	0	4	2%
180%	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	5	3%
190%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
200%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	4	2%

Figure 13 Choices vs Draws – Group F

The following table shows the results for Group F showing the frequencies gathered into Could Not Play (CNP), No Risk (NR), Risky (R) and Very Risky (VR) to indicate the response to the draw in the previous period:

	Rounds	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
	DRAWS	G	G	G	C	G	G	C	C	G	G	F	
Post G	CNP						9	0			0	0	9
	NR		0	0	0		0	0			0	0	0
	R		9	6	9		4	5			3	0	36
	VR		7	10	7		3	11			13	16	67
Post F	CNP												0
	NR												0
	R												0
	VR												0
Post C	CNP					16			16	12			44
	NR					0			0	0			0
	R					0			0	2			2
	VR					0			0	2			2
		0	16	160									

Figure 14 Riskiness of Choices Post Market Moves – Group F

note: 160 results not 176 because there are no results for period 1

Overwhelmingly results show a general appetite for risk (43% very risky and 24% risky while the remainder, 33% were bound by *Could Not Play* states), with no riskless choices being made, this is despite candidates being informed that they will only be paid for their performance, but suggests that they consider the odds of one crash in ten to be sufficiently low to be worthy of taking risks (reflecting economic cycles in the real economy). They were sufficiently motivated to take risks by the payoff (maximum of £10 as it turned out due to the draws and allowing for perfect timing of the market, compared to £14.00 in the Control Group) and not motivated not to take risk by the lack of pay off (a player placing all zero risk choices would only earn £1.3m or £1.30, although how many players calculated this at the outset is unclear, but would make for a relevant question for feedback questionnaires in future experiments). There is a 30 per cent increase in high risk taking in round two of the game, but this is then returned in the third round, suggesting either this is trial and error during a learning period or gambler's fallacy/hot hand phenomenon with anticipation of a forthcoming crash. Unfortunately, the rounds do not continue for long enough before the first crash to derive much further information from this result. Also of interest is the appetite for risk for those still able to play in round six that suggests their risk taking was not curtailed by the crash; alternatively that they were sufficiently motivated by status inflation to take further risks or they believed that a second crash was even less likely.

When the remaining players resumed participation in round seven, almost 70 per cent took high risk and no players took the riskless choice, which suggest a loss aversion or status inflation. This increased in the following rounds to over 81 per cent and 100 per cent respectively. The results from this are inconclusive and it is difficult to determine status inflation from loss aversion from gambler's fallacy. To this end study of the control group is necessary.

The following tables provide the same information for Group C:

DRAWS	G	G	G	G	C	G	F	F	F	G	G	Total	%
0%	0	0	0	0	0	11	4	0	0	0	0	15	10%
50%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
100%	1	1	0	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	9	6%
110%	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	4	3%
120%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
130%	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	5	3%
140%	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1%
150%	1	0	3	0	5	1	2	1	4	0	2	19	13%
160%	1	2	1	3	2	0	2	3	2	3	3	22	15%
170%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
180%	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	3%
190%	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1%
200%	8	8	6	8	2	1	4	7	4	8	7	63	44%

Figure 15 Choices vs Draws – Group C

	Rounds	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
	DRAWS	G	G	G	G	C	G	F	F	F	G	G	
Post G	CNP		0	0	0	0		4				0	4
	NR		1	0	2	1		1				0	5
	R		1	6	0	8		2				2	19
	VR		11	7	11	4		6				11	50
Post F	CNP								0	0	0		0
	NR								1	1	1		3
	R								2	6	0		8
	VR								10	6	12		28
Post C	CNP						11						11
	NR						0						0
	R						1						1
	VR						1						1
		0	13	130									

Figure 16 Riskiness of Choices Post Market Moves – Group C

note: 160 results not 176 because there are no results for period 1

Similarly, there were few zero risk choices overall (6% compared to 0% in the FULL Group), but very risky choices accounted for 61% of all choices (up from 43%) and yet risky choices fell to 22% from 24%. Crucially, Could Not Plays were reduced to 12% from 33%. Unfortunately, this disparity makes useful comparison difficult and as suggested previously parallel games (with uniform draws) might yield more useable results in future. In the initial periods there is a slight pattern of up-down-up-down in very risky choices compared to down-up-down in the FULL group. This indicates possible gambler's fallacy. Following a crash risk taking initially declines, contra to loss aversion theory, but then resumes with a up-down-up pattern. Interestingly, the final round does not show the 100% very risky choice (consistent with loss aversion theory) with 15% of subjects selecting a merely risky choice even though this was their final opportunity to bet big.

Again, in part due to the difference in draws little can be gained at first glance from analysis of the above data of the two groups. Indeed, a strategy for data analysis was calculated to evaluate selections/choices of subjects, using a step by step methodology, as follows (*note: T=current time period; T-1 is the period before; and T-2 is two periods before*):

- 0) *Able to Play (i.e. not banned/prohibited): Yes/No*
- 1) Choice: Not Risky, Risky or Very Risky?
- 2) Change on Previous Choice? (Period T-1)
- 3) Change Positive or Negative? (and to what degree?)
- 4) Did the Market Change? (Growth, Flat-line or Crash? – Change or No Change?)
- 5) Change Positive or Negative?
- 6) Was Change With or Against Market?

Generally, this reflected a: was the choice risky, was it a change from before, in which direction and was it in response to the market or against the market and how did this compare to previous choices? Unfortunately, this methodology becomes incredibly cumbersome when using more than a handful of subjects and so a simplified approach was adopted, using econometric regression methods, which simplifies to (as indicated previously):

current choice (\tilde{Y}_t) = previous choice (β_1) \pm status from previous round (β_{2t-1}) + error term (ϵ)

Here, status is measured in wealth in each round relative to the market wealth. The regression analysis was conducted using Excel add-in functions. Could Not Play results were excluded from the analysis by zeroing scores in the relevant sections of the data. For clarity the percentage LTV choices, previous round and current (that were used in the regression) were converted to decimals rather than percentages. Furthermore, status was calculated by:

- i) applying a scale of 10.00 = house purchase, 5.00 = bond purchase and 1.00 = cash deposit;
- ii) houses, bonds and cash deposits for each subject in each round had the scale applied and was then summed and the mean calculated for that round;
- iii) the relative "status" for each subject was then computed by subtracting the mean from the individual's "status" points in each round;
- iv) the relative status for the round previously was then used to calculate a change in status from the round before that (two periods previous to the current period) and the change in status was then used in the regression with the previous choice against the current choice.

note: for this reason the regression started in round 3 in order to provide the relevant data.

Unfortunately, this methodology whilst simplifying the regression also means the loss of two periods of panel results for each test group, and significantly whilst the first period was set as the establishing round, the second was likely to show significant status inflation results (particularly relevant in the Group F, where 3 rounds were crashes and so provided no useful information). The other drawback of this methodology model is that it does not capture results where status had already been achieved and was being maintained by continued risky/very risky choices. The differences between the two groups in terms of draws, the number of crashes in the Group F play and the small scale of the experiment all contribute to the limited conclusions that may be drawn from the result, which were as follows:

FULL Experiment		CONTROL Experiment	
<i>Regression Statistics</i>		<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.886515331	Multiple R	0.60571504
R Square	0.785909431	R Square	0.36689071
Adjusted R Square	0.782872686	Adjusted R Square	0.35578353
Standard Error	0.364051641	Standard Error	0.518327802
Observations	144	Observations	117

Figure 17 Regression Statistics – R-squared

FULL

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	2	68.59935998	34.29967999	258.7998866	6.41396E-48
Residual	141	18.68723724	0.132533597		
Total	143	87.28659722			

Figure 18 ANOVA - Group F

CONTROL

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	2	17.74891823	8.874459114	33.03184902	4.83376E-12
Residual	114	30.62766297	0.26866371		
Total	116	48.3765812			

Figure 19 ANOVA - Group C

FULL

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	0.134539344	0.039356141	3.41850956	0.000823437
Previous	0.920492714	0.0407324	22.59853863	1.01985E-48
Status Change	-0.024471573	0.01173359	-2.08559981	0.03881704

Figure 20 Coefficients, SE, t stat & P-values - Group F

CONTROL

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	0.792524781	0.09725475	8.148957014	5.2564E-13
Previous	0.521020204	0.064126126	8.12492876	5.95907E-13
Status Change	-0.027785457	0.012504119	-2.222104364	0.028250361

Figure 21 Coefficients, SE, t stat & P-values - Group C

As can be seen from the foregoing regression outputs, the majority of explanatory power is derived from the previous period choice rather than from the Status Change variable. The critical values of the t distribution at the 5 per cent level were 1.96 and 1.98 for 143 and 114 degrees of freedom respectively. The t statistics therefore show that both the Previous Choice Variable and Status Change Variable are statistically significant at the 5% level. Whilst the standard errors are relatively low in both cases, it is only the coefficient for the Previous variable that is noticeable. The R-squared and Adjusted R-squared suggest that much of the present choice is explained by the variables in the FULL model (approximately 80%) and only around one third in the CONTROL model, which would suggest prima facie that status inflation was a contributory factor, however this is also likely to be more to do with a better fit of data from the Previous Variable in the Full group compared to the Control (with increased slope coefficient and t stat), rather than the Status Change Variable. When considering the null hypothesis $\beta_s = 0$ the following two-tailed test was conducted:

Reject $\beta_s = 0$ if $\frac{\beta_s}{SE(\beta_s)} > \pm 1.64$ with the results:

-2.086 Group F and -2.216 Group C, suggesting that we can reject the null hypothesis. So we can say with 95% confidence that Status Change is statistically significant.

However it is reasonable to conclude that the results are inconclusive with regards to Status Inflation. Primarily because:

- i) the coefficient was very small;
- ii) the three crashes in the Full experiment means there was less useable data;
- iii) the difference in frequency in crash draws between groups was significant;
- iv) the sample size was small;
- v) the game could continue for longer to derive more data and a fuller picture (this would also reduce the potential for subjects non-comprehension error);
- vi) data was discarded due to the analysis methodology, which may have been significant;
- vii) the methodology of results analysis does not allow for the measurement of those that maintain relative status with continued risk taking, as opposed to changes in risk taking.

CONCLUSION

5. CONCLUSIONS

Whilst the literary logic may be based on sound reasoning, the Loan Game, on this occasion and in these two experiments failed to prove the existence of Status Inflation outright (although it was statistically significant). As observed by Moldovanu et al (2007) *"status is only partly determined by...monetary compensation."*

Further experiments need to be conducted of larger sample groups and with parallel control and full group experiments to make for more meaningful comparison. In addition, a new methodology for analysis could be developed that takes account of status maintenance actions as well as changes to risk taking. As mentioned the game could also be extended for more rounds.

The Loan Game could also be simplified to just two purchase items with a wider spread of returns to make results more pronounced and easier to measure (however a balance needs to be struck between this and unfairly weighting the odds too heavily on the risk taking side). This would of course also make mathematical calculations easier in results analysis.

The Loan Game may also, by virtue of the random nature of draws that do not build up the "boom" gradually, period on period (as often happens in the real world) be subject to many different influences that create noise around the status inflation measure, particularly gambler's fallacy and/or hot hand phenomenon.

An interesting additional possibility in this regard might be to make the business cycle endogenous to the model, so that, for example, as more people bought houses the price of houses would go up until confidence collapsed. The only problem with this notion is any added complications to the running of the experiment and/or analysis of the results – clearly there would be less experimental control of certain aspects, but the framing environment created would be a better representation of the real world.

We conclude that further experimentation is needed to confirm or disprove the hypothesis, however there is a not insubstantial cost associated with the running of experiments. One possible alternative might be, to publish the loan game on the internet (on a website), such as with the Beer Game (www.beergame.org), once the experiment has been refined, enhanced, sharpened and perfected. Other participants could then conduct their own experiments and feedback the results to a central pool for analysis (the results of which could then be constantly automatically/semi-automatically updated on the website).

In addition, the Loan Game could possibly be developed into a board game for non-research purposes.

If *Status Inflation* could be definitively proven, the findings could be significant as far as the design of incentive schemes, methods of employment and the intervention of government in wealth redistribution are concerned.

Thus:

- Firms should not encourage the employment of identical candidates, but instead encourage diversification that allows different people to succeed and be recognised for their previous achievements (endowed status) as well as those of their current role. The suggestion is that a multitude of individuals operating at the same top flight level, replicating effort, with the same information/education/training (the same tools to do the job), all striving and being motivated to outperform each other, can instead be replaced with
 - a) a smaller number of the top flight who just execute actions and
 - b) a greater number of individuals contributing to their success through their own particular specialisms. The status and contribution of these to the collective success would then be recognised and rewarded - celebrating diversity and rejecting homogenisation.

- The hiring of those in supervisory roles who have worked their way up the tree (internally or externally to the firm), rather than purely attending prestigious seats of learning (or achieving ever more qualifications prior to entry of the job market), provides a management team with more than a mere understanding of operations, but one liable to warrant and instil a respect that avoids, short-termism and status envy/insecurity.
- Governments should be wary of taking actions to unilaterally rebalance wealth distribution without requiring increased effort from the beneficiaries, as this is also liable to stimulate status inflation and all of the inherent dangers that this study suggests it encourages.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX I

LOAN GAME SAMPLE PAGES

EARNING YOUR BONUS							
YOU		YOUR NEIGHBOUR		YOUR NEIGHBOUR			
Name + ID Number		Name + ID Number					
<i>to be filled in each round by Loan Officer (you)</i>		<i>filled in each round by Credit Committee (your neighbour)</i>		<i>to be filled in each round by Credit Committee Officer</i>			
LOAN OFFICER		CREDIT COMMITTEE		CREDIT COMMITTEE			
Year	loan to Value	Approved	Declined	Market Move	Bonus		
<i>(round)</i>	<i>50%-200% in 10% increments</i>	<i>sign/initial in box</i>		<i>Crash = C, Flat = F, Growth = G (given by Investigator)</i>	<i>See table on the board (or below)</i>		
1	trial year	trial year	trial year	trial year	trial year		
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							
7							
8							
9							
10							
11							

Loan to Value	50%	100%	110%	120%	130%	140%	150%	160%	170%	180%	190%	200%
Equivalent Bonus if "G"	100,000				500,000					1,000,000		
Equivalent Bonus if "F"	100,000				100,000					100,000		
Equivalent Bonus if "C"	0				0					0		
Ban if "Crash" Ball Drawn	0				1 year					2 Years		

EARNING YOUR BONUS						SPENDING	
YOU		YOUR NEIGHBOUR		YOUR NEIGHBOUR			
Name + ID Number	Terry 6200368	Name + ID Number	Nick 6200342				
<i>to be filled in each round by Loan Officer (you)</i>		<i>filled in each round by Credit Committee (your neighbour)</i>		<i>to be filled in each round by Credit Committee Officer</i>		<i>to be filled in each round by Credit Committee Officer</i>	
LOAN OFFICER		CREDIT COMMITTEE		CREDIT COMMITTEE		LOAN	
Year	loan to Value	Approved	Declined	Market Move	Bonus	House	Investment
<i>(round)</i>	<i>50%-200% in 10% increments</i>	<i>sign/initial in box</i>		<i>Crash = C, Flat = F, Growth = G (given by Investigator)</i>	<i>See table on the board (or below)</i>	<i>(£1m each)</i>	<i>(£1m each)</i>
1	50%	nick		G	100,000		1
2	100%	nick		G	100,000		2
3	110%	nick		C			3
4	170% 160% nick	nick	nick	ban			4
5	180%	nick		G	2,000,000		5 x1
6	140%	nick		F	100,000		6
7	150%	nick		F	100,000		7
8	150%	nick		G	500,000		8
9	100%			G	100,000		9
10	50%			G	100,000		10
11	180%			G	2,000,000		11 x1

mistakes should be crossed through with a single line and the new amount written nextdoor & signed/initialled by the credit committee

Loan to Value	50%	100%	110%	120%	130%	140%	150%	160%	170%	180%	190%	200%
Equivalent Bonus if "G"	100,000				500,000					1,000,000		
Equivalent Bonus if "F"	100,000				100,000					100,000		

APPENDIX II

INSTRUCTIONS TO AND FOR THE ASSESSOR

Preparation

1. Purchase 20 ping pong balls (14 white/yellow, 4 blue & 2 orange) + opaque bag ideally with draw string to hold ping pong balls and then to draw the balls from.
2. Number subjects 1, 2, 3 & 4 (either as they enter the room or once seated passing along the rows) and repeat until all have an assigned number.
3. Assessor should divide the class into 4 quarters and direct the subjects to the relevant quarter by their allocated number (to split up groups of friends who will usually try to sit together):

Back of Class

3s	4s
1s	2s

Assessor

Front of the Class

4. Each player is given a "Loan Sheet" (for noting their Loan Officer/Credit Committee decisions), on the reverse of which is the investment decision table (incl. a compound interest table to facilitate easier calculations for players as they participate in the game and a totals table to fill for their own benefit during/after the game).
5. Players should then be put into pairs – both play role of loan officer and credit committee. If there is an odd player with no partner left over, they should assume the role of "Analyst", who will:
 - a. Help conduct the draws of the ping pong balls from the bag; and
 - b. fill in the Analyst Sheet for the on screen feedback mechanism.
6. The game must then be explained to the whole group, including the probability of draw for each "state-of-the-market" ball.
7. The game is then played, round by round and then the "Loan Sheets" are gathered at the end for analysis.

When the Game Begins

8. Each player (as loan officer) fills in their name/student number at the top of the left hand column the "Loan Sheet" in the box provided and then they fill in the detail of their Credit Committee Office in the box at the top of the middle column on the "Loan Sheet".

YOU		YOUR NEIGHBOUR	
Student Name + Number	TERRY 6200324XX	Student Name + Number	Nick 6200365XX
to be filled in each round by Loan Officer		to be filled in each round by Credit Committee Officer	
Year	loan to Value	Approved	Declined
(round)	50%-200% in 10% increments	sign/initial in box	

9. Each player (as loan officer) fills in their "offer" "Loan-to-value" (LTV) in the left hand table (the right hand column of that table), at a value of 50%-200% in 10% increments:

YOU	
Student Name + Number	TERRY
to be filled in each round by Loan Officer	
Year	loan to Value
(round)	50%-200% in 10% increments
1	50%
2	
3	
4	
5	

based on the bonus they aspire to achieve:

SUMMARY PAYOFF TABLE												
Loan to Value	50%	100%	110%	120%	130%	140%	150%	160%	170%	180%	190%	200%
Equivalent Bonus if "G"	100,000	500,000	1,000,000									
Equivalent Bonus if "F"	100,000	100,000										
Equivalent Bonus if "C"	0	0										
Ban if "Crash" Ball Drawn	0	1 year								2 Years		

10. The Loan Sheet is the passed to the Credit Committee Officer for approval or decline, indicated by the Credit Committee Officer initialling in the respective box for that period in the middle column.

YOUR NEIGHBOUR		
<i>Student Name + Number</i>	<i>Nick</i>	<i>620</i>
<i>to be filled in each round by Credit Committee Officer</i>		
Approved	Declined	
<i>sign/initial in box</i>		
<i>Nick</i>		

11. Once approved or declined, the sheet is returned to the Loan Officer. Any changes or amendments made prior to the ball being drawn may be done so with a single line strikethrough and must be initialled by the Credit Committee Officer.
12. Once all players have completed each of these two tasks for the corresponding period, which is indicated by players holding the Loan Sheet in the air above their heads, then, and only then should a ball be drawn (*blind*) from the bag (which should be opaque in order to avoid active selection – the balls also need to be uniform in size and shape). No changes may be made after the ball has been drawn.

Summary Process Illustration

Player 1

Player 2

13. The state-of-the-market is determined by the colour of the ball as described previously and the ball is held aloft for players to see and the result is called out.

14. The analyst records the result in the table.
15. Players learn whether they received their bonus (or face a *BAN*) following the draw and then must decide which investment to make from the table overleaf from their LTV offer table on the Loan Sheet and put a cross and number in their column choice e.g. "Cash" ...period 1...x1 or "House" ...period 3...x1:

SPENDING YOUR BONUS		
<i>to be filled in each round by YOU</i>		
House	Investment	Cash
<i>(\$1m each)</i>	<i>(\$0.5m each)</i>	<i>(\$0.1m each)</i>
-	-	X 1
-	-	-
X 1	-	-

16. The players should then read across to the compound interest table to see what value their investment has for that period and fill in the total table for the corresponding period (also overleaf and to the right of the investment choice table on the Loan Sheet).

Probabilities	State of the Market	Aggregate Investment (numbers of investments)			Aggregate Investment (value of investments)			ORANGE - Complete			
		to be filled in each round from show of hands			to be filled in each round from show of hands			House	Investment	Cash	
		House	Investment	Cash	House	Investment	Cash				
70%	Growth = G										
20%	Flatline = F										
10%	Crash = C										
1	G	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	2,593,742	1,079,462	134,392
2		0	0	0	0	0	0	10	2,357,948	999,502	130,477
3		0	0	0	0	0	0	9	2,143,589	925,465	126,677
4		0	0	0	0	0	0	8	1,948,717	856,912	122,987
5		0	0	0	0	0	0	7	1,771,561	793,437	119,405
6		0	0	0	0	0	0	6	1,610,510	734,664	115,927
7		0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1,464,100	680,244	112,551
8		0	0	0	0	0	0	4	1,331,000	629,856	109,273
9		0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1,210,000	583,200	106,090
10		0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1,100,000	540,000	103,000
11		0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1,000,000	500,000	100,000
TOTALS		0	0	0	0	0	0				
10x Randomly Drawn Sample Variable Sequences (drawn by excel generate random variable)											
Year	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Periods Used
1	Trial Year - Always 1 (Growth)										1
2	1	1	1	0	0	-1	1	1	0	1	0
3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
4	1	1	-1	1	1	1	-1	0	-1	1	0
5	-1	1	0	0	-1	1	1	0	1	0	0
6	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-1	1	1	0
7	1	-1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0
8	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	-1	1	0
9	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
10	-1	-1	-1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
11	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0
Totals											Averages
Growth	7	6	6	8	6	7	8	6	6	7	7
Decline	1	2	2	2	3	2	1	3	2	3	2
Crash	2	2	2	0	1	1	1	1	2	0	1
Total	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

Probabilities	State of the Market	Aggregate Investment (numbers of investments)			Aggregate Investment (value of investments)			ORANGE - Complete			
		to be filled in each round from show of hands			to be filled in each round from show of hands			House	Investment	Cash	
		House	Investment	Cash	House	Investment	Cash				
70%	Growth = G										
20%	Flatline = F										
10%	Crash = C										
1	G	0	3	17	0	3,238,387	2,284,658	11	2,593,742	1,079,462	134,392
2	G	2	8	10	4,715,895	7,996,019	1,304,773	10	2,357,948	999,502	130,477
3	G	8	8	4	17,148,710	7,403,721	506,708	9	2,143,589	925,465	126,677
4	C	0	0	4	0	0	491,950	8	1,948,717	856,912	122,987
5	F	0	0	4	0	0	477,621	7	1,771,561	793,437	119,405
6	G	10	5	5	16,105,100	3,673,320	579,637	6	1,610,510	734,664	115,927
7	G	12	3	5	17,569,200	2,040,733	562,754	5	1,464,100	680,244	112,551
8	G	15	0	5	19,965,000	0	546,364	4	1,331,000	629,856	109,273
9	F	15	0	5	18,150,000	0	530,450	3	1,210,000	583,200	106,090
10	C	0	0	5	0	0	515,000	2	1,100,000	540,000	103,000
11	G	8	7	5	8,000,000	3,500,000	500,000	1	1,000,000	500,000	100,000
TOTALS		70	34	69	101,653,906	27,852,180	8,299,914				
10x Random Variable Sequences, drawn by excel (use 1x if actual ball draw not possible)											
Year	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Periods Used
1	Trial Year - Always 1 (Growth)										1
2	1	1	1	0	0	-1	1	1	0	1	1
3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	1	1	-1	1	1	1	-1	0	-1	1	1
5	-1	1	0	0	-1	1	1	0	1	0	1
6	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-1	1	1	1
7	1	-1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1
8	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	-1	1	1

18. Once the results have been recorded, the analyst switches the on-screen view from the entry table to the feedback sheet (which also shows an automatically calculated cumulative market progress graph, as well as copies of the bonus/ban payoff table and the compound interest values table):

the completed form could appear as follows:

19. Once completed for each round the process is repeated until the end of the game and a total of 11 rounds have been played (including the initial establishing round). During the course of the experiments it was not possible to utilise the computer display and so the results illustrated above were manually written on the white board.
20. A brief period is be allowed for individuals to calculate their scores, following which all forms must then be collected and participants thanked for their time.

APPENDIX III

PROTOCOL V4 (FEELE 2013)

Protocol for Conducting Economics Experiments at the Finance and Economics Laboratory at Exeter (FEELE)

The following document outlines the procedures any researcher should follow if conducting economics experiments using the FEELE laboratory.

Personnel

FEELE has a management team comprised of two co-directors, Professor Todd R. Kaplan and Professor Dieter Balkenborg. The laboratory manager is Tim Miller.

Participant Pool

FEELE has an existing database of active participants. These participants are undergraduate students from the University of Exeter as well as non-students. They are contacted at the beginning of each academic year and are invited to register with FEELE if they wish to participate in economics experiments.

Participants register their personal details on ORSEE, software specifically designed to optimise recruitment for economics experiments. This includes their name, gender, degree programme (if applicable), and e-mail address.

FEELE operates a strict policy on the confidentiality of the data provided by our participants. We do not share personal information on our participants with any outside parties.

Participant Recruitment

The recruitment of participants is managed through ORSEE. This allows for the participant sampling for a given session, or set of sessions, to be made conditional on any characteristics relevant to the study (e.g. gender).

Anyone wishing to conduct an experiment must contact the FEELE lab manager, Tim Miller, at least one week before the anticipated date of the experiment. This is so that the lab time can be scheduled and recruitment initiated.

Ethics in Research

FEELE follows the ethical guidelines for social science research set by the University of Exeter. As such, ethical approval for staff and student research must be sought wherever the methods require the participation of people.

The School's Research Ethics representative, Adrian Bailey, advises on ethical issues and leads the review process.

Applications for ethical approval are reviewed on a regular basis. Responsibility for ethical review of staff research projects lies with the School's Research Strategy Group, which reviews applications on a regular basis throughout the academic year. Research Strategy Group also takes responsibility for the review of ethical considerations relating to students on Undergraduate and Postgraduate taught programmes in the School.

Everyone who takes part in an experiment conducted at FEELE must sign an informed consent document outlining the rules under which FEELE operates. This states: "Once the session is under way, your continuing participation is voluntary and you have the right to withdraw at any time." The consent form is publically available.

In line with University of Exeter and the British Psychological Society's ethics policies, participants are fully informed about the nature of the study that they are considering participating in (they are not, however, informed about hypotheses) and must give their informed consent prior to participating. Participants are permitted to opt out at any time with no penalty and are allowed to withdraw their data subsequent to participating.

FEELE operates under the methodological paradigm of experimental economics. This means we do not allow experiments to be conducted at FEELE which involve participant deception.

Conducting Experiments

Experiments can take place at any time during normal hours of operation of the University. Experiments that take place after normal hours or over the weekend need approval from the Business School.

Experiments usually take place during term time in the FEELE lab, but that is not a pre-requisite to using FEELE resources. If not using the physical lab space, researchers are expected to make their own arrangements.

Unless it is a specific part of the experimental design, experimental participants should be paid in cash at the end of the experiment. Payments should be made individually and in private, so that subjects cannot observe others' earnings.

Post-Experimental Data Management

Data that is generated using servers at FEELE is immediately passed on to the researcher after each experiment. It is the responsibility of researchers to ensure that they abide by the terms of their data management plan.

GENERAL ETHICAL PRINCIPALS

Treating participants fairly. According to the Trochim (2006) at the Research Methods Knowledge Base (www.socialresearchmethods.net), there are a six key issues surrounding empirical research involving people:

- I) **Voluntary Participation** – subjects must not be coerced into participation. Captive audiences are may not be used, except for cases where informed consent has been given and no coercive pressure (positive or negative) has been applied.
- II) **Informed consent** – subjects must be fully informed of the procedures and risks associated with the research and must give their willing consent to take part or have the option to refuse consent.
- III) **Risk of harm** – subjects must not be exposed to either physical or psychological risk.
- IV) **Confidentiality** – details of responses and any personal information provided by subjects must be kept private and only made available to researchers involved in the experiment.
- V) **Anonymity** – not only must subject confidentiality be preserved, but responses should be provided on an anonymous basis (ideally even to the researcher by use of identification numbers rather than names and so on). Results should be presented anonymously or in aggregate form so as to not cause embarrassment or harm. Strict anonymity may not always possible to achieve in the context of all experiments.
- VI) **Right to Service** – this is particularly relevant to subjects who participate in medical experiment control groups who have not been given the treatment being tested. If the treatment being tested, but which they did not receive is proven to have beneficial effects, the subjects of the control group should be entitled to the same treatment. This is not likely to be of relevance in this study.
- VII) Finally and specific to this study, the top prize and participation fees must be made available to all subjects, except for the relevant control group subjects who must be made aware of what rules the non-control group subjects are playing under.

Additionally, ethical issues must be considered as they arise and referred to an arbitrating authority (typically an Institutional Review Board), whose role it is to assess these issues and suggest amended procedures where necessary. Furthermore, participants and/or whistle-blowers must be able to register or refer any complaints or concerns they have to the review board.

APPENDIX IV

RESULTS DATA

GROUP F																	
Period	Draw	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
1	G	120%	120%	160%	160%	160%	130%	160%	150%	160%	160%	150%	160%	120%	140%	130%	140%
2	G	160%	120%	150%	150%	150%	130%	110%	150%	160%	150%	160%	160%	160%	150%	160%	180%
3	G	130%	160%	150%	150%	160%	160%	110%	130%	110%	160%	160%	160%	160%	160%	160%	160%
4	C	130%	160%	150%	150%	160%	150%	110%	160%	110%	120%	160%	160%	160%	160%	110%	120%
5	G	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
6	G	0%	0%	150%	150%	0%	150%	0%	0%	160%	120%	0%	0%	0%	0%	180%	170%
7	C	140%	140%	160%	160%	160%	160%	160%	120%	160%	170%	160%	160%	160%	160%	130%	130%
8	C	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
9	G	200%	160%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	150%	150%
10	G	130%	160%	160%	160%	160%	150%	110%	180%	160%	160%	160%	160%	160%	160%	170%	170%
11	F	200%	160%	160%	160%	160%	160%	200%	180%	160%	160%	160%	160%	160%	160%	180%	200%

GROUP C														
Period	Draw	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1	G	200%	200%	200%	200%	190%	200%	200%	160%	150%	200%	100%	180%	200%
2	G	200%	130%	160%	100%	200%	200%	200%	160%	200%	200%	200%	180%	200%
3	G	200%	140%	200%	200%	200%	110%	150%	160%	130%	150%	200%	200%	150%
4	G	200%	160%	200%	100%	200%	200%	200%	160%	100%	200%	200%	160%	200%
5	C	110%	130%	200%	150%	150%	160%	100%	160%	150%	110%	200%	150%	150%
6	G	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	150%	0%	200%	0%	0%	0%	0%
7	F	200%	160%	0%	200%	200%	0%	150%	0%	150%	160%	0%	200%	100%
8	F	200%	130%	200%	200%	200%	160%	200%	160%	100%	160%	200%	200%	150%
9	F	200%	130%	150%	200%	200%	110%	100%	160%	150%	160%	200%	150%	150%
10	G	200%	180%	200%	200%	200%	160%	200%	160%	200%	160%	200%	200%	100%
11	G	200%	180%	200%	200%	200%	160%	150%	160%	150%	160%	200%	200%	200%

APPENDIX V

SUBJECT FEEDBACK

Note: not all subjects provided feedback (below is verbatim copy of the feedback provided)

Group F (Full Experiment); 9 of 16 subjects (56%):

- i) Male: *"the percentages for loan to value are grouped - so only really need 50,110 and 160% - the middle values make no difference to the bonus."*
- ii) Female: *"what was the difference between (e.g.) 110% and 150%? A lot of the choices to make seemed pretty obvious."*
- iii) Female: *"initially found it difficult to understand. Was there a difference within risk categories i.e. was there a difference between choosing 110%-150% or 160%-200%?"*
- iv) Female: *"being able to communicate with partner meant we could agree/disagree before the credit committee bit e.g. less likely to decline any proposed loan - felt more like a team than individuals."*
- v) Male: *"looked complex, but well explained. Should explain crash a bit better at the start."*
- vi) Male: *"My only feedback would be that I had no inclination to decline my neighbour's credit since she was sitting next to me. This could have been different if we were kept anonymous."*
- vii) Male: *"good experiment. Clear to see that loan officers are motivated by high returns, but simplification of the factors which affect decisions. In this game, the sole objective (really) was to get the highest bonus possible, which meant taking the most risk. we were not well rewarded because of the high number of crashes. but over another 11 periods the odds may have paid off better. if we had been cautious (50-100%) we could have earned at most £1.1m and with the crashes had £0.7m. If we had been slightly cautious (100-150%) we would have earned £3m. The risks we took ultimately paid off."*
- viii) Male: *"was a game of statistics. To get best result would have to gamble everytime, especially easy to gamble when 10% chance of crash. This thinking would mean that loan officers would want to take more risks for the bank. To change would need to change reward structure. e.g. having a reduction in previous bonuses earned if crash would definitely have changed thinking."*
- ix) Female: *"was a good game of risk. Thought it was very clever. Maybe it would be good to break down the table and give different payoffs (e.g. 5 different payoffs), but that may make the game too complicated. Good luck with your dissertation"*

Group C (Control Experiment); 4 of 13 subjects (31%):

- i) Male: *"I enjoyed the experiment. However it took me a few rounds to grasp its simplicity, which is why in round 5 I fortunately, and rather luckily put a lower percentage. If I had understood it earlier I certainly would have put a higher percentage and put 200% throughout."*
- ii) Male: *"o.c. diminishes for last two periods as been ineffective. Cash deposit. Why various 110-150, no diff for us"*
- iii) Male: *"Tested how much % was lent despite equal risk i.e. between 160% or 200%"*
- iv) Female: *"I didn't really understand the game unfortunately and was quite confused throughout. It didn't seem as controlled as previous FEELE experiments I've done"*

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